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NURSES AND MIDWIVES ' COUNCIL FOR GHANA
FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 1990

NURSING PAPER III 'B' (PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ THE QUESTIONS CAREFULLY AND ANSWER ONLY WHAT IS ASKED.
NO MARKS WILL BE GIVEN FOR IRRELEVANT MATERIAL. CREDIT WILL
BE GIVEN FOR SIMPLE, CLEAR, LEGIBLE HANDWRITING, GOOD
ENGLISH AND ORDERLY ORGANIZATION OF MATERIAL.

BOTH QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

TIME ALLOWED: 1 HOUR

QUESTION ONE

CHILD SURVIVAL STRATEGIES ARE BEING TALKED ABOUT ALL THE WORLD OVER.

- (A) LIST FOUR (4) CHILD SURVIVAL STRATEGIES. (8 MARKS)
- (B) OUTLINE THE PREPARATION OF SUGAR SALT SOLUTION IN THE HOME .
(12 MARKS)
- (C) DISCUSS CHILD SPACING IN RELATION TO CHILD HEALTH. (20 MARKS)

TOTAL - 40 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

W.H.O. TALKS ABOUT HEALTH FOR ALL BY THE YEAR 2000 AND GHANA TALKS
ABOUT PRIMARY HEALTH CARE FOR ALL BY THE YEAR 1990.

- (A) WHAT IS PRIMARY HEALTH CARE ? (5 MARKS)
- (B) ENUMERATE FIVE (5) COMPONENTS OF PRIMARY HEALTH CARE.
(10 MARKS)
- (C) DESCRIBE THE FUNCTIONS OF THE THREE (3) LEVELS OF PRIMARY
HEALTH CARE. (15 MARKS)
- (D) DESCRIBE THE LEVEL C STAFF. (10 MARKS)

TOTAL - 40 MARKS

PRELIMINARY STATE REGISTERED NURSING EXAMINATION
OCTOBER 2002

INTRODUCTION TO PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) With the aid of a sketch, describe the life cycle of the plasmodium malariae.
Sketch - 2 marks
Description - 8 marks
- (b) Describe the ways by which malaria can be prevented in a community.
(10 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) List TEN different information that you will collect during a community study.
(10 marks)
- (b) Describe the usefulness of FIVE of these information to the health of individuals in the community.
(10 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Explain FOUR ways each of how the following contribute to promote the health of the individual:

- (a) Care of the hands and feet (8 marks)
- (b) Care of the mouth (6 marks)
- (c) Exercise (6 marks)
-

FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - AUGUST, 2001
NURSING PAPER III 'B' (PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) Identify EIGHT groups of people who are more at risk of HIV/AIDS infection in the Ghanaian society. (8 marks)
- (b) Explain the education you will give to an HIV positive client on:
- (i) Diet (3 marks)
 - (ii) Personal hygiene (3 marks)
 - (iii) Sexual behaviour (3 marks)
 - (iv) Exercise/rest/sleep (3 marks)
 - (v) Occupation (3 marks)
- (c) List FOUR organisations that are involved in educational campaign against HIV/AIDS. (2 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) List TWO methods each of dry and wet refuse disposal. (6 marks)
- (b) Describe FOUR hazards each that may result from poor dry and wet refuse disposal. (14 marks)
- (c) Explain FIVE advantages of a deep pit latrine for a rural community with a population of 500 people. (5 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) State SIX possible reasons that you can assign to the sporadic outbreak of cholera in Ghana? (3 marks)
- (b) State EIGHT clinical manifestations of cholera. (8 marks)
- (c) Explain the steps you would take to assist in the prevention of cholera in a community. (14 marks)

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING DIPLOMA LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - 25TH-28TH MARCH, 2002

PAPER III 'B' (PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) Describe TWO types of home visiting that the public health nurse should embark on. (8 marks)
- (b) Explain SIX advantages of home visiting in providing "family centred care". (12 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) State SIX benefits derived from the under-five clinic to members of your community during a health forum. (6 marks)
- (b) How would you educate members at the health forum to prevent malaria in children. (14 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) Describe FIVE health problems related to urbanization. (10 marks)
 - (b) Describe the role you will play in assisting the urban poor to maintain proper environmental sanitation. (10 marks)
-

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FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 2000
NURSING PAPER II (SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING,
ORTHOPAEDICS, UROLOGY AND GYNAECOLOGY)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

✓ Mrs. Annor, 34, has been admitted with thyrotoxicosis. She is booked for thyroidectomy.

- (a) Describe the psychological preparation for Mrs. Annor prior to the operation. (6 marks)
- (b) Enumerate FOUR specific investigations that would be done prior to surgery. (4 marks)
- (c) Describe the post operative management under the following headings:
 - (i) Specific observations (6 marks)
 - (ii) Wound care (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

②

Mr. Peter Ogoe, aged 73 years, was admitted to the ward with benign prostatic hypertrophy for surgery. On admission he looks ill and febrile. He has difficulty in passing urine.

- (a) Name TWO methods of operation that may be used. (1 mark)
- (b) Enumerate FOUR other diagnostic signs and symptoms which Mr. Ogoe will present. (2 marks)
- (c) Name FOUR specific laboratory investigations that may be carried out. (2 marks)
- (d) i. Describe the psychological preparation of Mr. Ogoe. (2 marks)
- ii. Outline the post operative management for the first 48 hours. (13 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Describe the post operative management of patients with the following operations within the first 36 hours:

- ✓ (a) Haemorrhoidectomy *Answer for 2003* (8 marks)
- ✓ (b) Cataract extraction (6 marks)

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FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 2001
NURSING PAPER III'D' (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Kodjo Ansah, aged 7 months, is brought to the emergency room very weak with a history of diarrhoea and vomiting for 3 days.

- (a) Enumerate FOUR causes of diarrhoea and vomiting in infants. (4 marks)
- (b) State TEN clinical features that Kodjo will present. (5 marks)
- (c) How will you manage Kodjo for the first twelve hours after admission? (16 marks)

QUESTION TWO

A four-year old girl, Abena, is brought to the emergency room with convulsions. She has been diagnosed as having measles.

- (a) List TEN characteristic features of measles. (5 marks)
- (b) What nursing care will you give to Abena? (15 marks)
- (c) What signs and symptoms will make you suspect that Abena is developing the following complications of measles?
 - (i) Bronchopneumonia
 - (ii) Corneal ulceration
 - (iii) Otitis media
 - (iv) Laryngitis
 - (v) Encephalitis (5 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Kofi Kuma, 5 years, have been admitted to the children's ward for repair of hernia.

- (a) List the additional information/history you will need from the mother to make Kofi Kuma feel at home and comfortable. (15 marks)
- (b) What are the problems/anxieties of a hospitalised child? (10 marks)

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FINAL MIDWIFERY EXAMINATION - 1ST-5TH NOVEMBER, 1999

SUBJECT: MIDWIFERY

PAPER II 'B' - ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Ayeyidzom Akos, 35 weeks pregnant was admitted with a history of oedema of both feet, a blood pressure recording of 165/100mmHg. and general feeling of being unwell.

- (a) Describe how Madam Ayeyidzom should be nursed during the first 48 hours of her admission into a hospital ward. (12 marks)
- (b) State FOUR signs and symptoms which are indication of Madam Ayeyidzom, developing eclampsia and your nursing intervention. (8 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) State TWO deviations in labour that can be detected on a Partograph. (2 marks)
- (b) Describe the progress of labour at 8 a.m. and 12 noon as recorded on the partograph provided. (6 marks)
- (c) As a midwife, explain your action at 12 noon and the possible outcome of the labour. (10 marks)
- (d) Following delivery, what other information must you record on the partograph. (2 marks)

FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 2000
NURSING PAPER III 'B' (PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) What is a family? (3 marks)
- (b) Describe SEVEN areas that would be taken into consideration when caring for an aged person in the family. (14 marks)
- (c) Enumerate EIGHT factors that bring about instability in the family. (8 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Reports reaching the district health administration indicate that home visiting has declined in all the sub districts at Fantekwa.

- (a) What do you understand by home visiting? (2 marks)
- (b) List SIX possible reasons for the decline in home visiting. (6 marks)
- (c) Describe SIX factors that would assist to improve home visits in the area. (12 marks)
- (d) List FIVE advantages of home visiting (5 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Describe FIVE responsibilities of the school nurse under each of the following headings:

- (i) School meals (5 marks)
- (ii) Dental care (5 marks)
- (iii) Environmental inspection (5 marks)
- (iv) Management of a disabled child in the school (5 marks)
- (v) Involvement of parents in school hygiene inspection. (5 marks)

COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER IA: (PERSONAL AND COMMUNITY HYGIENE, COMMUNICABLE DISEASES AND SCHOOL HEALTH)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- Enumerate FIVE common causes of anaemia in school children. (5 marks)
- State the signs and symptoms of worm infestation. (5 marks)
- Describe TEN preventive measures which will help reduce worm infestation. (10 marks)

QUESTION TWO

During a community study at Kyekye-were, you observed that the community has poor drainage system.

- Explain SIX hazards associated with poor drainage to the community members. (12 marks)
- Describe FOUR measures you would take to ensure good drainage of waste water in the community. (8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

A mother brings her 8 month-old infant with fever and diarrhoea to your clinic. The infant has had his immunization up to date. As a community officer (CHO);

- What assessment will you make? (6 marks)
 - How would you manage this child? (9 marks)
 - What education would you give to the mother before she takes the child home? (5 marks)
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REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING DIPLOMA LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - 25TH-28TH MARCH, 2002

PAPER III 'D' (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Dede, 5 years old, is admitted to the paediatric ward with measles.

- (a) What are the prodromal signs and symptoms of measles? (4 marks)
- (b) Describe your nursing management of Dede. (12 marks)
- (c) State EIGHT complications of measles. (4 marks)

-QUESTION TWO

Kwame Kumi, 5 years old, is admitted to your unit with second degree burns of the face, trunk and right leg.

- (a) What percentage of surface area of Kwame's body is affected? (2 marks)
- (b) Describe your nursing management of Kwame giving reasons for your actions. (14 marks)
- (c) Give EIGHT complications of severe burns. (4 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Kodjo Atta, 3 years old, is admitted to your ward with Hirschsprung's disease for surgery.

- (a) Give EIGHT clinical manifestations of Hirschsprung's disease. (4 marks)
- (b) State FIVE nursing objectives in relation to Kodjo Atta's pre-operative care. (5 marks)
- (c) Describe the specific post-operative nursing management of Kodjo Atta. (11 marks)

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REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING AND REGISTERED MENTAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIC: OBSTETRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

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QUESTION ONE

- a. With a well labelled diagram covering $\frac{1}{3}$ of a page, describe the macroscopic structure of the fallopian tube.
- i. Diagram (3 marks)
 - ii. Description (10 marks)
- b. State **FIVE (5)** relations of the fallopian tube (5 marks)
- c. State the nerve supply and supports of the Fallopian tube (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Client G2 P0 12 weeks amenorrhoea reported at your facility with the history of slight vaginal bleeding and lower abdominal pains. She was diagnosed as having threatened abortion.

- a. State **FIVE (5)** causes of abortion (5 marks)
- b. How would you manage the patient from the time of admission till she is discharged. (10 marks)
- c. State **FIVE (5)** outcomes of threatened abortion. (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A. A 33 year old Para 6^{AA} woman was brought to your facility with her baby after 48 hours of delivery at home. Her temperature on examination was 39.2^{oC}, pulse was 102 beat per minute and her blood pressure read 130/70mmHg. She was diagnosed as having puerperal pyrexia.

- i. Describe how you would manage the above woman? (10 marks)
 - ii. How would you manage her baby's cord? (6 marks)
- B. How would you educate the woman on Lactational Amenorrhoea Method (LAM)? (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING AND
REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIA: PSYCHIATRIC/MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mrs. Yawa Bronya, a 30-year-old alcoholic is admitted to the female admission ward with severe anaemia.

- (a) State FIVE nursing diagnoses that relate to Mr. Bronya's alcoholic state.
(5 marks)
- (b) Describe any TEN steps you would take in the psychological management of the patient in the first 48 hours of admission.
(10 marks)
- (c) Describe FIVE ways in which you will give emotional support to the patient's family.
(5 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Ms. Adwoa Mensah was referred to the community psychiatric nurse after 6 weeks of admission to the psychiatric hospital for continuity of care.

- (a) Outline FOUR ways in which the community psychiatric nurse will be useful to Ms. Adwoa and her family. (4 marks)
- (b) While in the ward, how would the nurse know if Ms. Adwoa Mensah was ready to be discharged? (5 marks)
- (c) How would the nurse organize and ensure adequate participation in diversional activities in the ward? (8 marks)
- (d) State SIX benefits that a patient can derive from occupational therapy. (OT) (3 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Ms. Nelly has been admitted to Ward 6 of the General Hospital with complaints of dryness of mouth, increased heart beat and sleepless nights. She was diagnosed as suffering from anxiety reaction.

- (a) Discuss FOUR ways by which Ms. Nelly's behaviour will disturb her family members. (4 marks)
- (b) Outline TEN reasons why a patient will refuse food. (5 marks)
- (c) Enumerate EIGHT reasons why Ms. Nelly will have sleepless nights in the ward. (4 marks)
- (d) What nursing management will you render to Ms. Nelly? (7 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

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**REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING AND
REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIF: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Serwaa is admitted into your ward with the diagnosis of acute otitis media.

- (a) Explain the term, otitis media. (In not more than 30 words). (4 marks)
- (b) Enumerate SIX clinical features of otitis media. (6 marks)
- (c) What would be your specific nursing management for the first 48 hours on admission? (6 marks)
- (d) List FOUR instruments that are required in syringing of the ear. (4 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Jonas, 62-years, was involved in a road traffic accident. She was found unconscious and has sustained compound fracture of the left tibia and fibula.

- (a) How would you manage Mrs. Jonas before she is transported to the nearest clinic? (12 marks)
- (b) State FIVE principles of fracture management. (5 marks)
- (c) Explain the following terms:
 - i. mal-union
 - ii. non union
 - iii. delayed union (3 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Madam Adowa Mensah brought her nine-year-old son to the eye clinic with a history of itching and redness of both eyes for three days. On examination he was diagnosed as having conjunctivitis.

- (a) State FOUR causes of conjunctivitis. (4 marks)
- (b) Describe the nursing management of Madam Adowa Mensah's son under the following headings:
 - i. care of the eyes (6 marks)
 - ii. drug management (4 marks)
- (c) How would you educate mother and son about prevention of eye infection? (6 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING AND REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIF: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Serwaa is admitted into your ward with the diagnosis of acute otitis media.

- (a) Explain the term, otitis media. (In not more than 30 words). (4 marks)
- (b) Enumerate SIX clinical features of otitis media. (6 marks)
- (c) What would be your specific nursing management for the first 48 hours on admission? (6 marks)
- (d) List FOUR instruments that are required in syringing of the ear. (4 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

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TOTAL – 20 MARKS

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 - ii. drug management (4 marks)
- (c) How would you educate mother and son about prevention of eye infection? (6 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH NURSING AND
REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIB: PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

(a) As an up and coming nurse in your community:

- i. Enumerate EIGHT categories of people who deserve special attention during home visiting. (4 marks)
- ii. Give FOUR importance of home visit. (4 marks)

(b) What steps would you follow in planning a health programme for the people in your community? (6 points)

(c) List SIX components of environmental hygiene. (6 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

- (a) Mention FOUR types of waste. (4 marks)
- (b) Explain FIVE ways by which food can be made wholesome under each of the following stages or levels:
 - i. Production stage
 - ii. Transportation stage (10 marks)
- (c) List SIX components of environmental hygiene. (6 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

A household pest is any creature or insect which is a nuisance and causes harm to the individual.

- (a) List FOUR household pests apart from the housefly. (4 marks)
- (b) Mention and describe SIX preventive measures that can be adopted to control the breeding of houseflies. (12 marks)
- (c) List FOUR diseases that can be spread by the housefly. (4 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH AND REGISTERED
COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIC: OBSTETRIC NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

(a) With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering about one third of a page, describe the microscopic structure of the breast.

(12 marks)

(b) State the benefits of breastfeeding under the following headings:

i. Mother (three benefits) (3 marks)

ii. Baby (five benefits) (5 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Madam Akoto was rushed to the labour ward shortly after spontaneous delivery of a baby girl on her way to the hospital.

- (a) Describe how you will manage the third stage of labour. (12 marks)
- (b) Describe SIX observations that would be recorded on completion of the 3rd stage of labour. (6 marks)
- (c) Mention FOUR drugs used in controlling haemorrhage during the 3rd stage of labour. (2 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Examination of the newborn is paramount in obstetric nursing because it affords the opportunity to detect early and manage any abnormalities that might pose danger to the newborn.

- (a) Describe the examination you would conduct on a newly born baby under the following headings:
 - i. Head and face (8 marks)
 - ii. Trunk (5 marks)
 - iii. Upper and lower extremities (5 marks)
 - iv. Genitalia (2 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

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**STATE REGISTERED NURSING EXAMINATION
NOVEMBER 2004**

PAPER III A (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) State SIX characteristics of a person who can be described as being mentally healthy. (6 marks)
- (b) You have been invited to give a health talk to a group of parents on the topic "Promoting Mental Health in the family". What salient points would you include in your talk? (8 marks)
- (c) In what ways can effective communication enhance efficiency in the activities on your ward? (6 marks)
- (d) Explain with examples the term "Defence Mechanism" (5 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) State EIGHT causes of mental subnormality. (4 marks)
- (b) Explain how mental retardation can be prevented. (6 marks)
- (c) State SEVEN predisposing causes of schizophrenia. (7 marks)
- (d) State EIGHT causes of non-compliance of psychotropic drugs by patients. (8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Nana Yaa, 16 years old, has been on admission on your ward with chest pains. You took her to the x-ray department for a chest x-ray and she suddenly started having grandmal seizures.

- (a) How would you manage the situation? (14 marks)
 - (b) What education would you give to Nana Yaa and relatives prior to discharge? (7 marks)
 - (c) State FOUR psychological problems Nana Yaa is likely to face in the community. (4 marks)
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REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSURE EXAMINATION - NOVEMBER 2004

PAPER I (MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Okata, aged 24, is on your ward with nephrotic syndrome.

- (a) Draw and label the longitudinal section (macroscopic structure) of the kidney. (5 marks)
- (b) Describe the pathophysiology of nephrotic syndrome. (6 marks)
- (c) How will you manage Mr. Okata regarding the following:
 - i. oedema (5 marks)
 - ii. diet (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Francis Mensah, 47 years old, is admitted to the medical ward with a diagnosis of typhoid fever.

Cholera

- (a) List SIX clinical features that Francis will present during the first week. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe the nursing management of Francis under the following headings:
 - i. observation (6 marks)
 - ii. nutrition (5 marks)
- (c) How can typhoid infection be prevented? (6 marks)

Cholera

QUESTION THREE ✓ RGH

Mr. Kwao Madey, aged 40, was admitted to the ward with enlarged abdomen. On abdominal examination, he was diagnosed as suffering from cirrhosis of the liver. He is booked for paracentesis abdominis.

- (a) Give FOUR causes of cirrhosis of the liver. (2 marks)
- (b) List EIGHT clinical manifestations of cirrhosis of the liver. (4 marks)
- (c) Describe your nursing responsibilities in paracentesis abdominis
 - i. during the procedure (6 marks)
 - ii. after the procedure (8 marks)

QUESTION FOUR ✓ RM

Mrs. Ansah, a 30 year old trader is rushed to the casualty department with severe shortness of breath, cough, wheezing and fatigue. She is diagnosed as suffering from acute bronchial asthma.

- (a) Mention FOUR factors that may precipitate an attack of Bronchial Asthma. (2 marks)
 - (b) Draw a comprehensive plan for the care of Mrs. Ansah under the undermentioned headings using the clinical manifestations below:
 - i. shortness of breath
 - ii. cough
 - iii. fatigue

Nursing diagnosis (3 marks)
Objective/outcome criteria (3 marks)
Nursing intervention (9 marks)
 - (c) Enumerate SIX complications of asthma. (3 marks)
-

**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH AND REGISTERED
COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIC: OBSTETRIC NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

(a) With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering about one third of a page, describe the microscopic structure of the breast.

(12 marks)

(b) State the benefits of breastfeeding under the following headings:

i. Mother (three benefits) (3 marks)

ii. Baby (five benefits) (5 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Madam Akoto was rushed to the labour ward shortly after spontaneous delivery of a baby girl on her way to the hospital.

- (a) Describe how you will manage the third stage of labour. (12 marks)
- (b) Describe SIX observations that would be recorded on completion of the 3rd stage of labour. (6 marks)
- (c) Mention FOUR drugs used in controlling haemorrhage during the 3rd stage of labour. (2 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Examination of the newborn is paramount in obstetric nursing because it affords the opportunity to detect early and manage any abnormalities that might pose danger to the newborn.

- (a) Describe the examination you would conduct on a newly born baby under the following headings:
- i. Head and face (8 marks)
 - ii. Trunk (5 marks)
 - iii. Upper and lower extremities (5 marks)
 - iv. Genitalia (2 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING
AND REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIIE: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A client on your ward developed coryza whilst on admission.

(a) How will you define coryza to a first year student nurse? (In not more than 30 words)

(2 marks)

(b) State SIX signs and symptoms of coryza.

(3 marks)

(c) Discuss the nursing management of coryza under the following headings:

i. Prevention of spread of infection

(6 marks)

ii. Medication

(4 marks)

iii. Nutrition

(4 marks)

(d) List TWO complications of coryza.

(1 mark)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Hypertension, a "silent killer," is said to be a sustained elevation of systolic blood pressure of 140mmHg and a diastolic of 90mmHg in a young adult.

- (a) Mention the TWO main types of hypertension. (2 marks)
- (b) Explain EIGHT aetiological factors of secondary hypertension. (4 marks)
- (c) State TWO examples each of the causes of secondary hypertension under the following headings:
 - i. Renal parenchyma disorders (2 marks)
 - ii. Endocrine disorders (2 marks)
 - iii. Central nervous system disorders (2 marks)
- (d) What education will you give to a hypertensive client on discharge? (8 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Mr. George Ayiso has been admitted to your ward with a diagnosis of bronchial asthma.

- (a) State SIX aetiological factors that contribute to bronchial asthma. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe the pathophysiology of bronchial asthma. (6 marks)
- (c) List SIX clinical manifestations of bronchial asthma. (3 marks)
- (d) What nursing management will you give to the client under the following headings:
 - i. Airway maintenance (4 marks)
 - ii. Prevention of recurrent attacks (4 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - NOVEMBER 2004**

PAPER III C (OBSTETRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) Describe the microscopic structure of the vagina. (9 marks)
- (b) What health education will you give during antenatal care to prevent vaginal infections? (8 marks)
- (c) List THREE abnormal vaginal discharges with their causative organisms. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

You are a rotational nurse assigned to the labour ward of your hospital. Madam Ami, a non attendant, is admitted in labour.

- (a) What obstetrical history will you collect from Madam Ami? (8 marks)
- (b) Give FOUR reasons for performing vaginal examination in labour. (4 marks)
- (c) State FOUR causes of delayed second stage. (4 marks)
- (d) Give FOUR abnormal conditions of the vulva which are of interest to the obstetric nurse. (4 marks)

...../2

QUESTION THREE

Madam Asana, with thirty-two weeks gestation, is admitted to the antenatal ward with severe Pregnancy Induced Hypertension (PIH).

(a) What will be your management of Madam Asana under the following headings:

- i. rest (4 marks)
- ii. observations (6 marks)

(b) Mention TWO effects each of PIH on:

- i. mother (2 marks)
- ii. foetus (2 marks)

(c) Give characteristics of progestin-only contraception under the following:

- i. THREE advantages (3 marks)
 - ii. THREE disadvantages (3 marks)
-

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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING
EXAMINATION - MARCH 2006**

PAPER IIID (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A twelve day old baby Kodjo is admitted to the ward with the diagnosis of pyloric stenosis. He is booked for operation.

- (a) Explain the term pyloric stenosis. (4 marks)
- (b) Write FIVE assessment findings the nurse will make which indicate that Kodjo actually has pyloric stenosis. (5 marks)
- (c) List TWO types of operation that can be done for an infant with pyloric stenosis. (2 marks)
- (d) Describe how you would manage Kodjo pre-operatively. (9 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Esi, a pre-term baby, is admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) for expert care.

- (a) What do you understand by the word "pre-term?" (2 marks)
- (b) Outline THREE measures by which the rate of pre-term births can be reduced. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

(c) State THREE abnormalities EACH, that you would observe, record and report on the underlisted when nursing the pre-term baby.

- i. colour
- ii. respiration
- iii. feeding
- iv. skin
- v. stools

(15 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Aba Kakraba, 5 years old, is diagnosed as having worm infestation.

(a) State FOUR common types of worms that Aba could be infested with, and describe the route by which each of them enters the body.

(6 marks)

(b) Mention the effects of ascariasis on the victim.

(7 marks)

(c) What education would you give to Aba's mother on prevention of worm infestation in Aba?

(7 marks)

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER I1IA (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Ama Atta, a newly married young woman, finds it difficult to cope with her responsibilities as a wife. She started feeling extremely uncomfortable and the doctor diagnosed her as having anxiety neurosis.

- (a) State FIVE differences between neurosis and psychosis. (5 marks)
- (b) State TEN physical signs and symptoms of anxiety. (5 marks)
- (c) How would you counsel Ama as to how to go about the situation. (10 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Kofi Nkum, 10 years old, is a mentally subnormal boy who stays at home with the mother.

- (a) List EIGHT predisposing causes of mental subnormality. (4 marks)
- (b) Describe FOUR psychological and social problems that the mother would face in caring for Kofi. (8 marks)

Kofi.

- Denial
- Anger
- Depression
- Stigmatization
- Guilt
- Isolation

...../2

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

(c) What education would you give to a community regarding prevention of mental subnormality.

(8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

(a) State FOUR predisposing factors in the aetiology of schizophrenia.

(4 marks)

(b) State EIGHT characteristic features of hebephrenic (disorganized) schizophrenia.

(4 marks)

(c) What advice would you give to a family who are predisposed to schizophrenia as a preventive measures.

(8 marks)

(d) State FOUR contraindications and FOUR side effects of largactil chlorpromazine.

(4 marks)

Hepatic disorder
Prostatic hypertrophy
Comatose pt
People with known hypersensitivity to phenothiazine

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LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH - 9TH MAY 2001

PAPER IIIIC: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mrs Ebel, a known sickler who is 28 weeks pregnant is admitted to your ward with sickle cell crisis and is to be transfused.

Describe the preparation you would make prior to her transfusion? (8 marks)

Mention EIGHT observations you would make on the patient during blood transfusion. (8 marks)

State FOUR measures you would take to alleviate the woman's pain during the crisis. (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mrs Cudjoe, 31 years old, with 32 weeks pregnancy has been admitted to the ward with the diagnosis of hypertension. Her blood pressure is 160/110 mmHg.

Explain the term "hypertension" in NOT more than TWENTY-FIVE words.

(2 marks)

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

(c) How would you manage Mrs. Cudjoe under the following?

- I. rest (6 marks)
- II. diet (9 marks)

QUESTION THREE

A 36 year old puerperal mother was brought to your ward with severe diarrhoea of unknown origin.

- a) State FOUR factors that may lead to diarrhoea. (4 marks)
- b) How would you prevent the other patients on the ward from being infected if the diagnosis of infective diarrhoea is established? (12 marks)
- c) State FOUR possible treatments that may be prescribed by the doctor. Give an example in each case. (4 marks)

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LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH - 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Akua Mainoo, 28 years old, gravida 3, para 1+1, has reported at the antenatal clinic for booking.

- (a) What past obstetric history would you take from her? (6 marks)
- (b) Describe the education that would be given to Madam Akua on nutrition. (6 marks)
- (c) What advice would you give to Madam Akua in relation to the following minor disorders of pregnancy:
- i. heart burn (4 marks)
 - ii. constipation (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

The partograph is a tool used for monitoring progress of labour.

- (a) Explain SEVEN advantages of the partograph to a student midwife on your ward. (7 marks)
- (b) State THREE categories of pregnant women who do not qualify for the use of the partograph. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

C 1. Madam Josephine Ako 25 years old , G2 P1 at term, was brought to the labour ward in labour on the 1st of May, 2005 at 8.00am for admission. Using the partograph provided plot the following observations made on Madam Josephine Ako.

Time: 8.00am (Admission)

- Cervical dilatation - 3CM
- Descent of foetal head - 4/5th
- Uterine contractions -3 in 10 mins lasting between 20- 40secs
- Membranes - Intact
- Foetal Heart rate - 130b.p.m
- Moulding - +

8:30 -10.30am

- Foetal Heart - 134 b.p.m.
- Contractions -3 in 10 mins lasting between 20 - 40 seconds

10:30 -11:30 am

- Foetal Heart - 132 b.p.m
- Contractions -4 in10 mins lasting between 20 -40 seconds

12 noon

- Cervical dilatation - 6cm
- Descent of foetal head - 2/5th
- Uterine contraction - 4 in 10 mins. lasting over 40 seconds

- Foetal Heart Rate - 134 b p m
- Moulding - ++

(6marks)

ii. How would you assess maternal condition in labour? (2marks)

iii. Mention TWO groups of drugs that may be used during labour and give ONE example of each. (2marks)

QUESTION THREE

Madam Awusi Gado, with 6 weeks amenorrhoea, reports at the gynaecological clinic with slight vaginal bleeding. She complained of severe abdominal pain. Her general condition started deteriorating and ruptured ectopic gestation was suspected.

a. How would you manage Madam Gado before the arrival of the doctor using the following headings:

- i. FIVE observations (5marks)
- ii. THREE physiological preparations for surgery (3marks)
- iii. FOUR psychological preparations for surgery (4marks)

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NMTG. BEREKUM

- 14 -

QUESTION THREE CONT'D

- (b) Give SIX causes of bleeding in early pregnancy. (3 marks)
- (c) What advice will you give Madam Gado before discharge? (5 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

Madam Esi Brimah, multip of 2, 28 years old, delivered at the hospital on the 2/5/2005.

- (a) What examination will you carry out on her during the first one week using the following headings:

- | | | | |
|------|--------|-----------|------------|
| i. | breast | (4 marks) | |
| ii. | uterus | (4 marks) | (12 marks) |
| iii. | lochia | (4 marks) | |

- (b) Madam Esi was brought to the hospital on the 10th day after delivery with a history of post partum haemorrhage. Describe how the midwife will manage her before the arrival of the doctor. (8 marks)
-

Office

FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - AUGUST, 2001
NURSING PAPER III'D' (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Kojo Atta, 8 years, is brought into the emergency room in a delirious state with the history of fever, vomiting after meals for three days and abdominal pain. A provisional diagnosis of typhoid fever has been made.

- (a) What other signs and symptoms may Kojo Atta present? (4 marks)
- (b) Mention TWO investigations that may be done to confirm the diagnosis. (2 marks)
- (c) State FOUR other conditions that may be confused with Kojo Atta's diagnosis of typhoid fever. (4 marks)
- (d) Describe the nursing management of Kojo Atta under the following headings:
 - (i) observations (4 marks)
 - (ii) personal hygiene (3 marks)
 - (iii) prevention of spread of infection (8 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Josephine Addai, 1½ years old, admitted to the paediatric unit with second degree burns of the chest and abdomen.

- (a) What psychosocial support would you give to the parents of the child? (5 marks)
- (b) What observations will you make on the patient for the first 24 hours? (5 marks)
- (c) Describe the preparation you would make for dressing the affected sites. (include the ward, the patient and the trolley).

QUESTION THREE

Baby Kofi Tawiah, 10 months old, is admitted to the paediatric unit with a diagnosis of intussusception.

- (a) What are the clinical manifestations of intussusception?
(7 marks)
- (b) What would be your post operative management of baby Kofi Tawiah during the first 24 hours after surgery?
(15 marks)
- (c) State THREE complications of intussusception.
(3 marks)
-

LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH – 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER I A: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering one-third of a page, describe the female external genitalia (the vulva).

Diagram (4 marks)

Description (11 marks)

- (b) Enumerate FOUR abnormalities of the vulva (excluding pruritus vulvae) (2 marks)

- (c) What advice will you give to a pregnant woman with pruritus vulvae on account of candidiasis? (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Madam Stella Quaison, gravida 5, para 4 all alive, delivered a preterm baby boy weighing 2 kilogram at the maternity wing of your hospital.

- (a) Describe how you would manage baby Quaison under the following headings:
- i. maintenance of body temperature (5 marks)
 - ii. feeding (5 marks)
 - iii. prevention of infection (8 marks)

- (b) List TWO favourable and TWO signs of deterioration that baby Quaison may present. (2 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) As a midwife what observations would you make on baby Akua who has discharging eyes after twenty-four hours of birth? (5 marks)
- (b) What would be your specific management of baby Akua? (7 marks)
- (c) Describe how you would manage baby Akua who was delivered with an Apgar score of five. (8 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

Baby Yaa Manu is to be discharged home with her mother from Kwesimintsim Hospital 24 hours after delivery.

- (a) Describe the examination to be conducted on baby Yaa before she is sent home. (14 marks)
 - (b) How does the ovarian hormone oestrogen influence the young girl at puberty? (6 marks)
-

**STATE REGISTERED NURSING EXAMINATION
NOVEMBER 2004**

PAPER III A (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) State SIX characteristics of a person who can be described as being mentally healthy. (6 marks)
- (b) You have been invited to give a health talk to a group of parents on the topic "Promoting Mental Health in the family". What salient points would you include in your talk? (8 marks)
- (c) In what ways can effective communication enhance efficiency in the activities on your ward? (6 marks)
- (d) Explain with examples the term "Defence Mechanism" (5 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) State EIGHT causes of mental subnormality. (4 marks)
- (b) Explain how mental retardation can be prevented. (6 marks)
- (c) State SEVEN predisposing causes of schizophrenia. (7 marks)
- (d) State EIGHT causes of non-compliance of psychotropic drugs by patients. (8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Nana Yaa, 16 years old, has been on admission on your ward with chest pains. You took her to the x-ray department for a chest x-ray and she suddenly started having grandmal seizures.

- (a) How would you manage the situation? (14 marks)
 - (b) What education would you give to Nana Yaa and relatives prior to discharge? (7 marks)
 - (c) State FOUR psychological problems Nana Yaa is likely to face in the community. (4 marks)
-

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STATE REGISTERED MIDWIFERY EXAMINATION - 1ST-5TH MAY 2000.

MIDWIFERY

PAPER II 'B' - ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Ruby Osei, 32 year-old primigravida who reported to the ante natal clinic with 34 weeks gestation; has been admitted to your ward as having moderate pregnancy induced hypertension.

- (a) Describe the nursing management of Madam Osei during the first 48 hours of admission giving reasons for every action taken. *Rest, Diet, Urine Test, Kneel* (12 marks)
- (b) State THREE groups of drugs which may be used in the management of Madam Osei giving an example of each group. (3 marks)
- (c) List SIX maternal and FOUR foetal complications that may occur in Madam Osei. *Ceclupia, Hypertension, Premature Del., Hematological dist., Asphyxia foetalis, Placenta, Renal Failure, Liver Necrosis* (5 marks)

160/100

QUESTION TWO

Study carefully the partograph of Madam Adjoa Comfort and answer the questions that follow:

- (a) Explain what has happened to Madam Comfort's progress of labour from the time of admission up to 6.30 p.m. (10 marks)
- (b) What would you suspect is wrong with Madam Comfort? (1 mark)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) Describe the care you will give to Madam Fulera and her sixth baby within 48 hours after delivery at the hospital. (12 marks)
- (b) State EIGHT principles that may guide a good family planning counsellor whenever she is discharging her duties to a client. (8 marks)

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REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING DIPLOMA LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - OCTOBER 2002

PAPER I (MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

End - Dr

Madam Lartey Adam is on admission with the diagnosis of acute renal failure on account of intake of herbal preparation for severe constipation which led to severe diarrhoea. She is on peritoneal dialysis.

- How would you explain acute renal failure to a student nurse? (7 marks)
- Enumerate FOUR main causes of acute renal failure. (4 marks)
- What would you tell a student nurse who wants to know why Madam Adam is on peritoneal dialysis? (6 marks)
- State THREE complications of peritoneal dialysis. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Nana Mansah has been rushed into the emergency room with a history of severe diarrhoea, emaciation and cough for the past 2 weeks. The following nursing diagnoses have been made:

- Actual fluid volume deficit related to gastrointestinal disturbance (diarrhoea).
 - Loss of self-image related to weight loss (emaciation).
- Describe the nursing interventions that would be implemented to meet the diagnoses made. (10 marks)
 - What precautions would be taken to prevent infecting other patients if upon investigation, the diagnosis is confirmed as AIDS? (5 marks)
 - List FIVE pieces of advice that would be given to the relatives on discharge. (5 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mock

Madam Agnes Nti aged 48, in your ward has suddenly developed severe chest pains radiating to the left shoulder and dyspnoea. A medical diagnosis of myocardial infarction has been made.

- (a) As a charge nurse, explain the term myocardial infarction to the first year student nurse on your ward in not more than 50 (Fifty) words. (4 marks)
- (b) State FOUR other clinical features of myocardial infarction. (4 marks)
- (c) Draw a comprehensive plan for the care of Madam Nti based on the clinical manifestations mentioned in the case study, under the following headings:
 - (i) Nursing diagnosis (3 marks)
 - (ii) Expected outcome (3 marks)
 - (iii) Nursing orders (6 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

End - AT2

Madam Ekua Danso, a business woman is on admission with a diagnosis of acute gout affecting the big toe.

- (a) Enumerate SIX signs and symptoms that Madam Danso would present. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe the nursing interventions that would be implemented to relieve her pains. (10 marks)
- (c) Explain the education that would be given on nutrition. (5 marks)
- (d) List FOUR other conditions affecting metabolism. (2 marks)

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BEREKUM-B/A

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIID: PAEDIATRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

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NMT C
HOLY FAMILY HOSPITAL
BEREKUM-B/A

QUESTION ONE

A fourteen day old baby Abubakar is admitted to the ward with the diagnosis of pyloric stenosis. He is booked for operation.

- a. Write **SEVEN (7)** assessment findings the nurse will make to indicate that Abubakar actually has pyloric stenosis. (7 marks)
- b. State **TWO (2)** types of operation that can be done for an infant with pyloric stenosis. (2 marks)
- c. Describe how you would manage baby Abubakar preoperatively. (11 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A 5 year old child is admitted to the paediatric emergency unit with the diagnosis of febrile convulsion.

- ai. State **EIGHT (8)** typical manifestations suggestive of febrile convulsion. (4 marks)
- aii. Enumerate **EIGHT (8)** causes of Convulsive Disorders in children. (4 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing management you would give to the child for the first 24 hours. (10 marks)
- c. List **FOUR (4)** complications of febrile convulsion in children. (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A 20 year old mother has a three month old baby boy with cleft lip and palate. The mother has been advised to bring the child back to the hospital in a month's time for surgical repair.

- a. What would be the associated problems of the child? (4 marks)
- b. What steps would you take to reduce anxiety in the family and to help them cope with the problems? (5 marks)
- c. After repair of the cleft lip and palate describe how you would care for the infant under the following headings:
 - i. Prevention of postoperative injury (4 marks)
 - ii. Maintenance of adequate nutrition (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER IIIA: MENTAL HEALTH/PSYCHIATRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- A. A mother of two young children, was seen at the Out Patient's Department and diagnosed as having Neurotic Depression.
- i. State **TEN** possible causes of Neurotic Depression. (5 marks)
 - ii. List **TEN** clinical manifestations that the mother will present. (5 marks)
- B. Describe how you will manage the risk of suicide in the patient on your ward. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A tertiary student was brought to the hospital and admitted to the medical ward on account of showing abnormal behavior while writing examination. Provisional diagnosis of catatonic excitement was given

- a. State **EIGHT** specific features of excitement that you would observe to confirm the diagnosis. (8 marks)
- b. Describe how you would manage the patient within 6 hours before the patient is transferred to the Psychiatric Unit. (8 marks)
- c. Explain ^{the} **TWO** side effects **each** of the following major tranquilizers listed below to a junior nurse. (4 marks)
 - (i) Oculogyric crisis
 - (ii) Agranulocytosis

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. List **FIVE (5)** causes of Acute Delirium (5 marks)
- b. State **SIX (6)** psychological features of Delirium (6 marks)
- c. Describe the management of a Delirious patient within the first 48 hours of admission (9marks)

TOTAL = 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING AND
REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER IIIC: OBSTETRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Rosemond G1 P0 34 weeks pregnant delivered few hours ago at your facility. Describe how you would manage the baby under the following headings.

- ai. Warmth (5 marks)
- a.ii. Prevention of infection (5 marks)
- b. State **TEN** causes of preterm labour. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- A. Describe the past obstetrical history that would be obtained from Madam Aku Abbey, G2 P1, 24 weeks pregnant who has come to the antenatal clinic (10 marks)
- B. State **FIVE** observations each that you will make on
 - i. A primigravida who had a spontaneous delivery with a sutured episiotomy (5 marks)
 - ii. A baby who was spontaneously delivered (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A woman G1 P0 has been admitted to your ward with the diagnosis of Ruptured Ectopic pregnancy.

- a. State the signs and symptoms that the woman will exhibit. (6 marks)
- b. State **FOUR** investigations that will be requested. (2 marks)
- c. Describe the pre-operative procedure for this woman till she is taken to the theatre. (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING AND
REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIA: PSYCHIATRIC/MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mrs. Yawa Bronya, a 30-year-old alcoholic is admitted to the female admission ward with severe anaemia.

- (a) State FIVE nursing diagnoses that relate to Mr. Bronya's alcoholic state.
(5 marks)
- (b) Describe any TEN steps you would take in the psychological management of the patient in the first 48 hours of admission.
(10 marks)
- (c) Describe FIVE ways in which you will give emotional support to the patient's family.
(5 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Ms. Adwoa Mensah was referred to the community psychiatric nurse after 6 weeks of admission to the psychiatric hospital for continuity of care.

- (a) Outline FOUR ways in which the community psychiatric nurse will be useful to Ms. Adwoa and her family.

(4 marks)

- (b) While in the ward, how would the nurse know if Ms. Adwoa Mensah was ready to be discharged?

(5 marks)

- (c) How would the nurse organize and ensure adequate participation in diversional activities in the ward?

(8 marks)

- (d) State SIX benefits that a patient can derive from occupational therapy. (OT)

(3 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Ms. Nelly has been admitted to Ward 6 of the General Hospital with complaints of dryness of mouth, increased heart beat and sleepless nights. She was diagnosed as suffering from anxiety reaction.

- (a) Discuss FOUR ways by which Ms. Nelly's behaviour will disturb her family members.

(4 marks)

- (b) Outline TEN reasons why a patient will refuse food.

(5 marks)

- (c) Enumerate EIGHT reasons why Ms. Nelly will have sleepless nights in the ward.

(4 marks)

- (d) What nursing management will you render to Ms. Nelly?

(7 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING AND
REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIA: PSYCHIATRIC/MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mrs. Yawa Bronya, a 30-year-old alcoholic is admitted to the female admission ward with severe anaemia.

- (a) State FIVE nursing diagnoses that relate to Mr. Bronya's alcoholic state.
(5 marks)
- (b) Describe any TEN steps you would take in the psychological management of the patient in the first 48 hours of admission.
(10 marks)
- (c) Describe FIVE ways in which you will give emotional support to the patient's family.
(5 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Ms. Adwoa Mensah was referred to the community psychiatric nurse after 6 weeks of admission to the psychiatric hospital for continuity of care.

- (a) Outline FOUR ways in which the community psychiatric nurse will be useful to Ms. Adwoa and her family. (4 marks)
- (b) While in the ward, how would the nurse know if Ms. Adwoa Mensah was ready to be discharged? (5 marks)
- (c) How would the nurse organize and ensure adequate participation in diversional activities in the ward? (8 marks)
- (d) State SIX benefits that a patient can derive from occupational therapy. (OT) (3 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Ms. Nelly has been admitted to Ward 6 of the General Hospital with complaints of dryness of mouth, increased heart beat and sleepless nights. She was diagnosed as suffering from anxiety reaction.

- (a) Discuss FOUR ways by which Ms. Nelly's behaviour will disturb her family members. (4 marks)
- (b) Outline TEN reasons why a patient will refuse food. (5 marks)
- (c) Enumerate EIGHT reasons why Ms. Nelly will have sleepless nights in the ward. (4 marks)
- (d) What nursing management will you render to Ms. Nelly? (7 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY
AND REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER IIIIE: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE (3)** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A 30 year old lady was admitted to your ward with the diagnosis of cystitis. She is complaining of supra pubic pain

- a. Enumerate **EIGHT** clinical manifestations of cystitis (4 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing care you would give to the patient to relieve her pain (8 marks)
- c. Describe the education you would give to the patient to prevent recurrent urinary tract infection (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Eric Awadzi, 50, is admitted to the Medical Ward with cerebrovascular accident, CVA. He has left hemiplegia and is semiconscious.

- a. Enumerate **EIGHT** risk factors for the occurrence of CVA. (4 marks)
- b. Describe **EIGHT** clinical features that Mr. Awadzi would present. (4 marks)
- c. Describe how you would manage Mr. Awadzi for the first 48 hours (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Madam Aku shika, 30 years was brought to your ward through the casualty with the diagnosis of pneumonia.

- a. Enumerate **TEN (10)** predisposing factors of pneumonia (5 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing intervention she would receive under the following nursing diagnoses
 - i. Ineffective airway clearance (6 marks)
 - ii. Relief of chest pain and discomfort (9 marks)

TOTAL = 20 marks

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Kojo Atta, a 36 year old man was admitted to the hospital with perforated duodenal ulcer. He was booked for emergency laparotomy.

- a. State **FOUR** clinical manifestations of duodenal ulcer. (2 marks)
- b. How would you prepare Mr. Atta for surgery? (11 marks)
- c. What education would you give to Mr. Kojo Atta upon discharge. (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Alice Okanta, a 35 year old woman was rushed to the ward with second degree burn of the front trunk and both upper limbs. After assessment, she was put on Intravenous Infusion, Normal Saline 2 litres x 24hours, Ringer's lactate 1.5litres x 24hours.

- A.
 - i. Calculate the percentage of body burns using the Wallace's Rule of Nine. (3 marks)
 - ii. Calculate the flow rate of normal saline if the drop factor is 5 drops per minute. (5 marks)
- B. Describe the process of wound healing. (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Jerry King, 26, is admitted to the ward following a road traffic accident. He sustained fractured ribs and ruptured spleen. He is for splenectomy.

- a. State **FOUR** functions of the spleen. (2 marks)
- b. Describe the preoperative management of the patient under the following headings.
 - i. Physiological preparation (5 marks)
 - ii. Physical preparation (7 marks)
- c. State **SIX** complications that may occur after the operation. (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Madam Sadia Abubakar underwent cholecystectomy and was brought back to the ward with T-tube in situ.

- a. Enumerate **EIGHT (8)** clinical features of cholelithiasis. (4 marks)
- b. Describe the post operative care of Madam Sadia. (12 marks)
- c. Describe the preparation of Madam Sadia towards discharge within the first seven days. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

FEBRUARY 2017

PAPER I: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Kwaku Abu, a 25 year old man was rushed to your hospital with a history of fever and general body weakness. After assessment by the doctor on duty, a provisional diagnosis of Bacterial Meningitis was made.

- a. State **EIGHT (8) OTHER SPECIFIC** signs and symptoms of Kwaku Abu's condition (4 marks)
- b. List **TWO (2) SPECIFIC** diagnostic investigations with rationale that may be done to confirm the diagnosis (2 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing management of Kwaku Abu under the following;
 - i. Nutrition (7 marks)
 - ii. Health Education on discharge (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A 65 year old woman, was admitted to your ward with a diagnosis of right ventricular heart failure. She is a known hypertensive but non-compliant to treatment regimen and clinical reviews.

- a. Enumerate **FOUR (4)** predisposing factors of her condition. (2 marks)
- b. List **SIX** clinical features that she may present. (3 marks)
- c. Describe your nursing interventions to this patient under the following nursing diagnosis.
 - i. Activity intolerance and fatigue related to decreased carbon monoxide. (7 marks)
 - ii. Excess fluid volume related to heart failure syndrome. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

FEBRUARY 2017

PAPER II: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING, GYNAECOLOGY,
UROLOGY, ORTHOPAEDICS ETC.

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION THREE

Mr. Kojo Asempa, a 50 year old alcoholic is admitted to your ward with the diagnosis of cirrhosis of the liver. He presented with ascites and oedema of both feet.

- a. What nursing care will you give to Mr. Asempa under the following diagnosis?
 - i. Activity intolerance related to fatigue and weight loss (5 marks)
 - ii. Impaired skin integrity related to oedema formation (6 marks)
- b. Describe how you would care for Mr. Asempa **before** and **after** paracentesis abdominis. (9 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Mrs. Mabel Opoku-Nyinah 36 years, is admitted to the ward with a provisional diagnosis of duodenal ulcer. The doctor had requested for gastroduodenoscopy to be done to confirm the diagnosis.

- a. List **SIX (6)** clinical manifestations that Mrs. Opoku-Nyinah will present (3 marks)
- b. Describe the nurse's responsibilities under the following:
 - i. Before gastroduodenoscopy (7 marks)
 - ii. After gastroduodenoscopy (5 marks)
- c. How would you educate Mrs. Opoku-Nyinah on dietary management? (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

School Copy

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING DIPLOMA LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - OCTOBER 2002

PAPER III'A' (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A 20-year old student was admitted to the medical ward with the complaint of having "high fever". The doctor suspects catatonic excitement.

- State EIGHT specific features of catatonic excitement that you would observe to confirm the diagnosis. (4 marks)
- How would you manage the patient within 6 hours before he is transferred to the psychiatric unit? (8 marks)
- State EIGHT barriers to effective communication. (8 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Addo, 29 years old was admitted to your ward with gastritis. Later on he was showing signs of psychopathic behaviour.

- Explain the term psychopathic personality. (3 marks)
- State the THREE main types of psychopathy. (3 marks)
- What are the characteristic features of psychopathic behaviour? (7 marks)
- Describe how you would manage Mr. Addo regarding the psychopathic behaviour. (7 marks)

...../2

QUESTION THREE

- (a) Explain in NOT MORE THAN THIRTY WORDS the term 'conversion hysteria'.
(4 marks)

- (b) List SEVEN cognitive signs and symptoms associated with depression.
(7 marks)

- (c) Describe how mental disorders can be prevented in children. (9 marks)

LIBRARY
NMTC, BEREKUM

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

JANUARY 2009

PAPER I: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all FOUR questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Agya Koo, a newly diagnosed diabetic patient, is admitted to the medical ward.

- (a) Mention and explain THREE cardinal manifestations Agya Koo would present. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe the education you would give to him under:
- i. Care of hands and feet (5 marks)
 - ii. Exercise (4 marks)
 - iii. Prevention of hypoglycaemia (6 marks)
- (c) List FOUR complications of diabetes. (2 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Opanyin Yaw Atta, aged 50 years is on admission in your ward with the diagnosis of renal failure.

- (a) State THREE clinical phases of acute renal failure. (3 marks)
- (b) State FOUR causes each of acute renal failure under the following classifications:
 - i. Pre renal (2 marks)
 - ii. Intra renal (2 marks)
 - iii. Post renal (2 marks)
- (c) List THREE indications for initiating dialysis in chronic renal failure. (3 marks)
- (d) Describe peritoneal dialysis. (6 marks)
- (e) Discuss TWO specific assessment you would make on the urine sample of Mr. Opanyin Yaw Atta. (2 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

A 45-year-old man is admitted to the ward with swelling at the anal region and bleeding during defaecation. He is diagnosed as prolapsed haemorrhoids.

- (a) Describe the FOUR degrees of haemorrhoids. (4 marks)
- (b) List EIGHT predisposing factors for the condition. (4 marks)
- (c) State THREE diagnostic evaluations that could be carried out to confirm the disease. (3 marks)
- (d) What would be your nursing care for the prolapsed haemorrhoids. (9 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION FOUR

Adjoa Mansah, aged 21 years on your ward has been diagnosed of leukaemia. She is complaining of pain and anorexia.

- (a) Explain leukaemia to a junior nurse. (In not more than 30 words). (2 marks)
- (b) What would be your nursing interventions based on the following nursing diagnosis:
 - i. High risk for infection related to neutropaenia. (7 marks)
 - ii. Altered nutrition, less than body requirements related to anorexia. (5 marks)
 - iii. High risk for bleeding related to thrombocytopaenia. (6 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

LIBRARY
NMTCC BEREKUM

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING DIPLOMA LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - OCTOBER 2002

PAPER III'D' (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Adwoa Mansa, a very ill looking four year old child, is admitted to your ward and is to be tubefed.

- (a) Under what conditions will tube feeding be recommended for a sick child?
(5 marks)
- (b) Describe the procedure for passing nasogastric tube to feed Adwoa Mansa and the rationale for each step.
(15 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Amidu Baba, aged 12, is admitted to your ward with nephrotic syndrome.

- (a) State EIGHT clinical manifestations of nephrotic syndrome. (5 marks)
- (b) State THREE nursing objectives that you will set for Amidu and describe the appropriate interventions that will help you achieve the objectives set.
(Give 3 interventions for each objective). (12 marks)
- (c) What advice will you give to the parents on discharge of Amidu. (3 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Kofi Manu, 6 years old is admitted to your ward with intestinal obstruction for surgery.

- (a) List FIVE possible causes of intestinal obstruction in children. (5 marks)
 - (b) Describe the care you will give Kofi stating the objectives you hope to achieve. (9 marks)
 - (c) State TWELVE ways of preventing accidents to children on the wards. (6 marks)
-

**STATE REGISTERED NURSING EXAMINATION
NOVEMBER 2004**

PAPER III A (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) State SIX characteristics of a person who can be described as being mentally healthy. (6 marks)
- (b) You have been invited to give a health talk to a group of parents on the topic "Promoting Mental Health in the family". What salient points would you include in your talk? (8 marks)
- (c) In what ways can effective communication enhance efficiency in the activities on your ward? (6 marks)
- (d) Explain with examples the term "Defence Mechanism" (5 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) State EIGHT causes of mental subnormality. (4 marks)
- (b) Explain how mental retardation can be prevented. (6 marks)
- (c) State SEVEN predisposing causes of schizophrenia. (7 marks)
- (d) State EIGHT causes of non-compliance of psychotropic drugs by patients. (8 marks)

...../2

QUESTION THREE

Nana Yaa, 16 years old, has been on admission on your ward with chest pains. You took her to the x'ray department for a chest x'ray and she suddenly started having grandmal seizures.

- (a) How would you manage the situation? (14 marks)
 - (b) What education would you give to Nana Yaa and relatives prior to discharge? (7 marks)
 - (c) State FOUR psychological problems Nana Yaa is likely to face in the community. (4 marks)
-

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

JANUARY 2009

PAPER II: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all FOUR questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A thirty-five-year-old lady, Yaa Asantewaa, was rushed to the emergency unit of your hospital with generalized abdominal pains. She was diagnosed as having ruptured ectopic pregnancy.

- (a) Explain ruptured ectopic pregnancy to a first year student. (4 marks)
- (b) Enumerate SIX predisposing conditions to ectopic pregnancy. (6 marks)
- (c) State EIGHT clinical features that would be exhibited by Madam Yaa Asantewaa. (4 marks)
- (d) Describe the nursing intervention for Madam Yaa Asantewaa under the headings:
 - i. Pain (3 marks)
 - ii. Grieving (3 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Beak with large goitre is scheduled for a subtotal thyroidectomy to treat thyrotoxicosis.

- (a) State TEN clinical features of toxic goitre. (5 marks)
- (b) List FOUR specific diagnostic investigations of toxic goitre. (5 marks)
- (c) Describe the post-operative nursing management of Mrs. Beak for the first 48 hours. (8 marks)
- (d) List FOUR side effects of antithyroid drugs. (2 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Describe how you would prepare a patient for the following investigations after the procedure has been explained:

- (a) Barium meal (5 marks)
- (b) Bronchoscopy (4 marks)
- (c) Thoracentesis (6 marks)
- (d) Lumbar puncture (5 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION FOUR

Ms. Aba Krampah, aged 25 is admitted to your ward with a discharging sinus on her left upper arm for 6 months. On examination and investigations, she was diagnosed as osteomyelitis secondary to sickle cell disease.

- (a) List FOUR major organisms causing osteomyelitis. (4 marks)
- (b) Describe how you would take a wound swab from Aba's discharging arm. (Trolley has been sent to the bedside). (10 marks)
- (c) Name TWO possible surgical treatments for osteomyelitis. (2 marks)
- (d) What education would you give to patient on discharge? (4 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION
SEPTEMBER 2019**

PAPER I: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY TEST

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR (4)** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Alhaj Abdul Mumuni, aged 75, was admitted to a medical ward in a semi-conscious state and yet to be diagnosed. He however has a nasogastric tube in-situ for feeding.

- a) How would you feed him through the nasogastric tube? (10 marks)
- b) Describe how you would serve a bedpan to this Patient? (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Madam Akua Seima, a 36 year old petty trader was admitted to a female medical ward with the diagnosis of Pneumonia on account of difficulty in breathing, restlessness and a body temperature of 39°C. She was in a semi-conscious state. In the process of care, Madam Seima passed on after the fifth (5th) day.

- a) State **EIGHT (8)** predisposing factors of Pneumonia. (4marks)
- b) Identify **THREE (3)** actual health problems and state their respective nursing diagnosis. (6 marks)
- c) Describe how you will conduct the Last Offices. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Mr. Tia Amakye, a banker aged 55, is on admission at a medical ward with the diagnosis of Right Sided Heart Failure secondary to Hypertension.

- a) Enumerate **SIX (6)** signs and symptoms that Mr Amakye may present. (3 marks)
- b) State **FOUR (4)** laboratory investigations that may be carried out on Mr. Amakye. (2 marks)
- c) Describe the nursing care you will render to Mr Amakye for the first 24 hours. (9 marks)
- d) What education would you give to Mr Amakye on his general health prior to his discharge. (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Miss Yayra Agbo a 25 year old hair dresser, was rushed to the emergency ward in severe pain with the complaint of recurrent attacks of vaso-occlusive crisis in sickle cell disease. She was put on intramuscular injection of Diclofenac 75mg Stat. Miss Agbo's Haemoglobin read 7g/dl and was to be transfused.

- a) Outline **FOUR (4)** precautionary measures that you would observe during administration of the prescribed injection. (4 marks)
- b) What would be your nursing responsibilities before, during and after the blood transfusion? (10 marks)
- c) What health education would you give to Miss Agbo to prevent recurrent attacks of sickle cell crisis? (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

JANUARY 2009

PAPER I: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all FOUR questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Agya Koo, a newly diagnosed diabetic patient, is admitted to the medical ward.

- (a) Mention and explain THREE cardinal manifestations Agya Koo would present. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe the education you would give to him under:
- i. Care of hands and feet (5 marks)
 - ii. Exercise (4 marks)
 - iii. Prevention of hypoglycaemia (6 marks)
- (c) List FOUR complications of diabetes. (2 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Opanyin Yaw Atta, aged 50 years is on admission in your ward with the diagnosis of renal failure.

- (a) State THREE clinical phases of acute renal failure. (3 marks)
- (b) State FOUR causes each of acute renal failure under the following classifications:
 - i. Pre renal (2 marks)
 - ii. Intra renal (2 marks)
 - iii. Post renal (2 marks)
- (c) List THREE indications for initiating dialysis in chronic renal failure. (3 marks)
- (d) Describe peritoneal dialysis. (6 marks)
- (e) Discuss TWO specific assessment you would make on the urine sample of Mr. Opanyin Yaw Atta. (2 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

A 45-year-old man is admitted to the ward with swelling at the anal region and bleeding during defaecation. He is diagnosed as prolapsed haemorrhoids.

- (a) Describe the FOUR degrees of haemorrhoids. (4 marks)
- (b) List EIGHT predisposing factors for the condition. (4 marks)
- (c) State THREE diagnostic evaluations that could be carried out to confirm the disease. (3 marks)
- (d) What would be your nursing care for the prolapsed haemorrhoids. (9 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION FOUR

Adjoa Mansah, aged 21 years on your ward has been diagnosed of leukaemia. She is complaining of pain and anorexia.

- (a) Explain leukaemia to a junior nurse. (In not more than 30 words). (2 marks)
- (b) What would be your nursing interventions based on the following nursing diagnosis:
 - i. High risk for infection related to neutropaenia. (7 marks)
 - ii. Altered nutrition, less than body requirements related to anorexia. (5 marks)
 - iii. High risk for bleeding related to thrombocytopenia. (6 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING
EXAMINATION - MARCH 2006**

PAPER IIIA (MENTAL HEALTH/PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Adamu, a patient on your ward, was seen by the medical officer who diagnosed him as suffering from a psychosomatic disorder, precisely peptic ulcer.

- (a) Explain the term psychosomatic disorder (NOT MORE THAN 35 WORDS)
(3 marks)
- (b) What support would you give to Mr. Adamu under the following headings:
 - i. psychological (10 marks)
 - ii. physical (7 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Eku, 32 years old alcoholic, is admitted to the surgical ward with burns of the left leg for skin grafting. A day prior to the operation he started showing signs of confusion and restlessness. The doctor made a provisional diagnosis of alcoholic hallucinosis and put him under observation.

- (a) Outline the history that you would obtain to help establish the fact that the patient is dependent on alcohol.
(6 marks)
- (b) List SIX factors that contribute to alcoholism. (6 marks)
- (c) Describe how you would manage the patient for the first 48 hours after the provisional diagnosis has been made.
(8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

I. Kiki, an 18 year old boy, was admitted to your ward in a state of status epilepticus.

- (a) Explain the condition "status epilepticus". (3 marks)
- (b) Give THREE possible precipitating factors that can lead to status epilepticus in a patient with epilepsy. (3 marks)
- (c) Describe how you would manage Kiki on the ward. (10 marks)

II. A schizophrenic patient in your ward is granted 7 days parole by his doctor.

Give FOUR benefits that the patient will derive from going home for this short period. (4 marks)

**STATE REGISTERED NURSING EXAMINATION
NOVEMBER 2004**

PAPER III A (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) State SIX characteristics of a person who can be described as being mentally healthy. (6 marks)
- (b) You have been invited to give a health talk to a group of parents on the topic "Promoting Mental Health in the family". What salient points would you include in your talk? (8 marks)
- (c) In what ways can effective communication enhance efficiency in the activities on your ward? (6 marks)
- (d) Explain with examples the term "Defence Mechanism" (5 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) State EIGHT causes of mental subnormality. (4 marks)
- (b) Explain how mental retardation can be prevented. (6 marks)
- (c) State SEVEN predisposing causes of schizophrenia. (7 marks)
- (d) State EIGHT causes of non-compliance of psychotropic drugs by patients. (8 marks)

...../2

QUESTION THREE

Nana Yaa, 16 years old, has been on admission on your ward with chest pains. You took her to the x-ray department for a chest x-ray and she suddenly started having grandmal seizures.

- (a) How would you manage the situation? (14 marks)
 - (b) What education would you give to Nana Yaa and relatives prior to discharge? (7 marks)
 - (c) State FOUR psychological problems Nana Yaa is likely to face in the community. (4 marks)
-

**REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING AND
REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIIF: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Serwaa is admitted into your ward with the diagnosis of acute otitis media.

- (a) Explain the term, otitis media. (In not more than 30 words). (4 marks)
- (b) Enumerate SIX clinical features of otitis media. (6 marks)
- (c) What would be your specific nursing management for the first 48 hours on admission? (6 marks)
- (d) List FOUR instruments that are required in syringing of the ear. (4 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Jonas, 62-years, was involved in a road traffic accident. She was found unconscious and has sustained compound fracture of the left tibia and fibula.

(a) How would you manage Mrs. Jonas before she is transported to the nearest clinic?
(12 marks)

(b) State FIVE principles of fracture management. (5 marks)

(c) Explain the following terms:

i. mal-union

ii. non union

iii. delayed union (3 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Madam Adowa Mensah brought her nine-year-old son to the eye clinic with a history of itching and redness of both eyes for three days. On examination he was diagnosed as having conjunctivitis.

(a) State FOUR causes of conjunctivitis. (4 marks)

(b) Describe the nursing management of Madam Adowa Mensah's son under the following headings:

i. care of the eyes (6 marks)

ii. drug management (4 marks)

(c) How would you educate mother and son about prevention of eye infection?
(6 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

REGISTERED MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION (BASIC)

AUGUST 2013

PAPER I: PAEDIATRICS AND OBSTETRIC ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Niniako delivered a baby boy, four days ago. Baby was discovered having jaundice and have been planned to undergo phototherapy.

- a. As a midwife on duty, describe how you would manage the baby who is undergoing phototherapy (12 marks)
- b. State **EIGHT** complications of phototherapy that may occur if baby is not managed well (4 marks)
- c. Explain **EIGHT** causes of physiological jaundice. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Oestrogen as a hormone plays an important role in the development of secondary sex characteristics during and after puberty.

- A. What are the changes that occur in the female during and after puberty as a result of oestrogen? (8 marks)
- B. With your knowledge in family planning describe how you would educate a woman who wants to use the Calendar-Based Method as a way of preventing pregnancy. (12 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

A new born baby was brought to your clinic and was diagnosed as having cephalhaematoma.

- A. What are the characteristics of cephalhaematoma? (8 marks)
- B. How would you manage this baby? (4 marks)
- C. Describe **EIGHT** clinical manifestations that will be indicative of intracranial injury of babies. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

- A. Describe the macroscopic structures of the bladder. (10 marks)
(Diagram not required)
- B. Describe the effects of full bladder in labour. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

SEPTEMBER 2019

PAPER II: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING, GYNAECOLOGY, UROLOGY, ORTHOPAEDICS

ESSAY TEST

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR (4)** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Frank Ato, a 30-year-old mason fell from a storey building and sustained swelling and abrasions on the face. He was rushed to the emergency unit in a semi-conscious state. After series of assessments, he was diagnosed as having head injury. He has been scheduled for surgery when his condition stabilizes.

- a) Describe the immediate pre-operative nursing care you would give to Mr. Ato before the surgery (8 marks)
- b) What precautionary measures would you include in your health education to Mr. Ato prior to his discharge from the hospital (8 marks)
- c) State **EIGHT (8)** possible complications that Mr. Ato might have. (4 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Gomez Awuni, a 19-year-old student was involved in a road traffic accident and sustained fracture of the ribs with other minor lacerations on the body. Mr. Awuni was admitted to a surgical ward for further management after a chest x'ray was done.

- a) What **EIGHT (8)** clinical manifestations would Mr. Awuni present? (4 marks)
- b) Describe the first aid management of Mr. Awuni at the scene of injury before transporting him to the hospital. (8 marks)
- c) Describe the immediate care you would render to Mr. Awuni on his arrival at your hospital (5 marks)
- d) State **SIX (6)** possible complications of fractured ribs. (3 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Mrs. Hasmona Prinkles, a 67 year old house wife weighed 130 kg. Laparotomy was performed on her **(Five) 5** days ago on account of acute abdomen. She started complaining of severe pains and warmth at the operation site. On examination, the Nurse detected wound dehiscence with discharge.

- a) Explain the difference between **wound dehiscence** and **wound evisceration**? (4 marks)
- b) State **SIX (6)** causes of wound dehiscence. (6 marks)
- c) Describe the nursing care you would give to Mrs. Prinkles. (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION FOUR

Pastor Mike Agyeman, a 48-year-old long distance driver was admitted at the surgical ward with the history of constipation and inability to move his bowels for the past two weeks. On examination, there was sore at the anal region, impacted stools and haemorrhoids which sometimes bleeds. Pastor Agyeman has been booked for haemorrhoidectomy.

- a) State **FOUR (4)** signs and symptoms of constipation (2 marks)
- b) Describe the pre and post-operative care of Pastor Agyeman. (12 marks)
- c) Outline the education that you would give to Pastor Agyeman and his family to prevent the recurrence of haemorrhoids (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING

SEPTEMBER, 2018.

PAPER I: MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING

ESSAY TEST

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **FOUR** questions.
2. Each question carries **20 marks**.
3. Read the questions carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
4. Do not write in either margin.
5. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract marks.

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Abdulai Pimpim, a banker, was brought to the Medical Emergency unit of your hospital. On admission, his blood pressure was 180/120mmHg and subsequent ones checked also read between 105/110mmHg and 160/110mmHg. He was diagnosed of hypertension.

- a. List **ten (10)** factors associated with hypertension to a first year student Nurse. (5 marks)
- b. State the mechanism of action of the following antihypertensive medications.
 - i. Captopril
 - ii. Methyldopa
 - iii. Amlodipine
 - iv. Furosemide(4 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing management you will render to the patient under the following:
 - i. Lifestyle modification (4 marks)
 - ii. Monitoring and managing potential complications (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Bambo Kasasah, a 38-year-old unemployed was admitted to the male medical ward with a diagnosis of liver cirrhosis.

- a. List **four (4)** types of liver cirrhosis. (2 marks)
- b. State twelve (12) clinical manifestations that Mr. Kasasah is likely to exhibit. (6 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing management you would render to Mr. Kasasah under the following:
 - i. Skin care (6 marks)
 - ii. Nutrition (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Mr. Yaw Apensah, 45 years is admitted to the medical ward on account of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

- a. Describe the nursing management or interventions for the following nursing diagnosis:
 - i. Ineffective breathing pattern related to shortness of breath. (5 marks)
 - ii. Activity intolerance due to fatigue (5 marks)
- b. State the risk factors for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. (5 marks)
- c. Describe five (5) clinical features of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. (5 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTIONS FOUR

Mr. Ayi Mensah, a 65-year-old farmer, was admitted to the medical ward with a history of hiccups, anorexia, seizures and bleeding from the gastrointestinal tract. He was diagnosed of chronic renal failure after laboratory investigations indicated a higher than normal amount of urea and creatinine in his blood.

- a. State **ten (10)** clinical features of cardiovascular conditions associated with chronic renal failure. (5 marks)
- b. Apart from blood urea nitrogen (BUN) and creatinine levels, explain **three (3)** other diagnostic investigations that may be conducted. (3 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing management to be rendered to Mr. Mensah under:
 - i. Fluid volume deficit related to decreased urine output (6 marks)
 - ii. Imbalanced nutrition, less than body requirement related to anorexia, nausea and vomiting (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

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LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
MAY 2005

PAPER IIIB: PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING
ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

During a routine home visit you were called to attend to some community members who had a feast the previous day and are complaining of severe abdominal cramps, diarrhoea and vomiting. The people were suspected to be suffering from food poisoning.

- a) What is food poisoning? (2 marks)
- b) Describe SIX possible causes of food poisoning. (6 marks)
- c) What measures would you take to improve food hygiene in your sub-district? (12 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) What is home visiting? (2 marks)
- (b) Describe the preparation for home visit. (6 marks)
- (c) Explain SIX points you would lay emphasis on during a visit to a pregnant woman. (12 marks)

QUESTION THREE

In a village where you work, environmental sanitation is poor and malaria is on the increase.

Give FIVE clinical manifestations of malaria. (5 marks)

How would you as a practising midwife assist to prevent and control malaria among community members especially the pregnant women and children? (13 marks)

What is the current drug of choice for the treatment of malaria? (2 marks)

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LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH - 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER IIID: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Mary Atta, was brought to your hospital from a village with a history of labour pains which started 15 hours ago with no progress. The doctor has booked her for emergency Caesarean section.

- (a) Explain how you would prepare the patient physically for an emergency Caesarean section? (9 marks)
- (b) List EIGHT basic instruments you would use to set a trolley for the operation. (4 marks)
- (c) Describe how you would manage the patient for the first three hours after the operation. (7 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mrs Amina Yakubu, 35 years old underwent total hysterectomy on account of multiple myoma. A week later, her wound was detected to be infected.

- (a) Explain how Mrs. Yakubu might have acquired the infection. (10 marks)
- (b) List FOUR routes through which microorganisms may enter the body. (2 marks)

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

- (c) How would you teach a junior nurse on the technique of handwashing?
(6 marks)
- (d) Enumerate FOUR complications that she may develop apart from infection.
(2 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mrs. Janet Ainoo, 46 years old, married with one child is admitted to your ward with breast cancer. She is for radical mastectomy.

- (a) State SIX predisposing factors of breast cancer. (3 marks)
 - (b) State EIGHT signs and symptoms of breast cancer. (8 marks)
 - (c) What education would you give to Mrs. Ainoo and her family pre operatively in order to help them adjust to her new image. (7 marks)
 - (d) State TWO specific complications of mastectomy. (2 marks)
-

LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
MAY - 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER IIIA: MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 11 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Yaa Ginn, 16 years old, had spontaneous delivery in your facility. You observed Yaa sitting on the bed, looking moody and just gazing at her baby who was crying. She was later diagnosed as suffering from depression.

- Mention FIVE factors during the antenatal period that may lead to depression in the puerperium. (5 marks)
- State EIGHT other signs and symptoms that Yaa will present. (4 marks)
- How would you manage Yaa and the baby for the first 48 hours while at your facility? (11 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Adjo Avornyo, 27 years, gravida 2 para 1, is 10 weeks pregnant. She reports for antenatal care and reveals to the midwife that her first born, 4 years old is a Mongol (Down's syndrome). She is anxious and needs advice.

- Mention SIX factors during foetal and infancy that may be responsible for mental retardation. (3 marks)
- How would mental retardation affect the child? (7 marks)

...../2

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

c) What advice would you give to Adjo in order to reduce the risk of having another mentally retarded child? (10 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mame Yaa, 40 years old, gravida 12, para 11, all alive (girls) is on admission with the diagnosis of 34 weeks pregnancy with anxiety neurosis. On interviewing her you learnt that the husband was threatening to divorce her if she delivers another girl.

(a) Explain in NOT more than 30 words the term "anxiety". (3 marks)

(b) State TEN psychological features of anxiety. (5 marks)

(c) How would you manage Mame Yaa in order to reduce the anxiety? (12 marks)

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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED COMMUNITY NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIA: MENTAL HEALTH/PSYCHIATRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A 32 years old Senior High School teacher was knocked down by a motor bike. The facial outlook indicates someone who has been drinking. You have been asked to monitor the client for signs of alcohol withdrawal symptoms

- a. State **TEN (10)** signs and symptoms of alcohol withdrawal symptoms (10 marks)
- b. Mention **SIX (6)** factors that contribute to alcoholism (3 marks)
- c. Describe the nursing management of alcohol withdrawal symptoms within 48 hours (7 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. State **TEN (10)** physical manifestations of Senile Dementia (5 marks)
- b. Describe the nursing management of a patient with senile dementia under the following heading:
 - i. Protection from injury (5 marks)
 - ii. Psychological care (10 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- Ai. Mention **TEN (10)** effects of stigmatization on psychiatric patients (10 marks)
- Aii. State **FOUR (4)** measures that can be employed to prevent this stigmatization (4 marks)
- B. State **SIX (6)** functions, duties or roles of a Community Psychiatric Nurse (6 marks)

Total = 20 Marks

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED MENTAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIB: PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Measles is a highly infectious childhood disease with high fatality rates.

- a. Describe **NINE (9)** common signs and symptoms of measles. (9 marks)
- b. Mention **SIX (6)** complications of a child with severe measles. (3 marks)
- c. Describe the control measures of measles. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A village community was identified to dispose off their dry refuse indiscriminately.

- a. How would you convince the community members to desist from this practice (8 marks)
- b. How would you advice the use of the following methods for disposing of their refuse?
 - I. Incineration (5 marks)
 - II. Composting (5 marks)
- c. State **FOUR (4)** advantages of incineration? (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. State **FOUR (4)** benefits of family planning **EACH** to the mother and child. (8 marks)
- b. Describe the instructions you will give to a client on the use of:
 - i. Male condom (6 marks)
 - ii. Female condom (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIID: PAEDIATRIC NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Adwoa, a five-year-old girl is admitted to the paediatric unit with the diagnosis of severe kwashiorkor.

(a) In not more than FIFTY words, explain "kwashiorkor" to the mother. (3 marks)

(b) Describe FIVE predisposing factors leading to the condition. (5 marks)

(c) Describe any FOUR clinical manifestations that the child would present with. (6 marks)

(d) State any FOUR measures that could be taken in the prevention of kwashiorkor in the society. (6 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Abena, 9-month-old, is admitted to the children's ward with acute gastroenteritis. She has moved her bowels eight times with vomiting in the last 24 hours.

- (a) State THREE major causes of gastroenteritis. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe EIGHT clinical manifestations that she may present. (8 marks)
- (c) Describe the nursing intervention you would carry out within the 1st 48 hours. (9 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Kofi Ackah, a 10-year-old boy was admitted to the children's ward as a referred case from Nyanyano Health Post, with provisional diagnosis of bacterial meningitis.

- (a) State FOUR causative organisms of meningitis. (2 marks)
- (b) i. State SIX clinical features of bacterial meningitis. (3 marks)
ii. List TWO investigations that can be carried out to confirm the diagnosis. (1 mark)
- (c) Describe the nursing management of Kofi Ackah. (12 marks)
- (d) Enumerate FOUR complications of meningitis. (2 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

**REGISTERED-GENERAL NURSING LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - NOVEMBER 2003**

PAPER III'D' (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Kwame Oduro, 6 years old, is admitted into the paediatric ward with a temperature of 39⁰C, anorexia and dysuria. He has been diagnosed as having urinary tract infection.

- (a) Give the pathophysiology of urinary tract infection. (8 marks)
- (b) Enumerate THREE objectives in the nursing management of Kwame Oduro. (6 marks)
- (c) Describe THREE nursing interventions that you will perform for Kwame to help you achieve your aim. (6 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Yaw Musa, 4 years old, was brought to the out-patient department with scabies.

- (a) What education would you give to the mother on the management of the condition at home? (12 marks)

Baby Akua, 6 weeks old, has been admitted to your ward with tetanus.

- (b) Describe the nursing management of baby Akua under the following headings:
 - i. control of spasms (4 marks)
 - ii. nutrition (4 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) How would you manage Kwame Danso, 3 weeks old baby who has been brought in from home with bleeding circumcision? (5 marks)
- (b) What is the nursing management of a 6-year old boy from theatre after toileting a 2nd degree burns on his abdomen, using the underlisted headings:
- i. wound care (5 marks)
 - ii. education of mother on prevention of burns and scalds at home (5 marks)
- (c) What advice would you give to the mother of a child with gastro enteritis on discharge? (5 marks)
-

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER IIIA (MENTAL HEALTH/PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) State SIX characteristics of a mentally healthy individual. (6 marks)
- (b) What salient points would you include in your talk to a focused group of parents on "promoting mental health in the family." (8 marks)
- (c) In what ways can effective communication enhance efficiency in the activities on your ward? (6 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Madam Yaa Adu, 76 years old, is admitted to the medical ward with malaria. Observations revealed that she also has senile dementia.

- (a) Explain the term "senile dementia". (4 marks)
- (b) State TEN clinical features of senile dementia. (5 marks)
- (c) On discharge, what education would you give to the family members on how to manage Madam Adu at home? (11 marks)

QUESTION THREE

On the 3rd day after admission into the medical unit, Akua Akowuah, a 19 year old student suffering from diabetes mellitus, was found to be very anxious and agitated.

- (a) State SIX possible reasons why Yaa is anxious. (3 marks)
 - (b) What measures would you take to reduce her anxiety? (10 marks)
 - (c) Give SEVEN advantages of recreational therapy. (7 marks)
-

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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - NOVEMBER 2004**

**PAPER II (SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING, ORTHOPAEDICS,
UROLOGY AND GYNAECOLOGY)**

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Miss Rose Donkor, 32 years old, is admitted into your ward in a collapsed state. She is diagnosed as having ruptured ectopic pregnancy.

- (a) Explain the term ruptured ectopic pregnancy. (In not more than FIFTY words)
(4 marks)
- (b) Enumerate EIGHT clinical features that Miss Donkor will present.
(4 marks)
- (c) State your interventions for the following nursing diagnoses:
- i. alteration in comfort (pain) related to ruptured tubal pregnancy.
 - ii. grieving related to the loss of pregnancy
 - iii. knowledge deficit related to ectopic pregnancy.
- (12 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Louis Gra, 39 years old, is admitted to the surgical unit with brain tumour. He is to undergo craniotomy.

- (a) List FOUR specific investigations that would be carried out prior to surgery.
(4 marks)

...../2

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

(b) Describe the post operative management of Mr. Enin within the 1st 48 hours under the following headings:

- i. observations (9 marks)
- ii. care of wound (4 marks)

(c) List SIX specific post operative complications that may occur following craniotomy. (3 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mrs. Oyibo, aged 45, was admitted to your ward with chronic cholecystitis. She is scheduled for cholecystectomy.

(a) State your nursing interventions for the following nursing diagnosis before and during operation.

High risk for wound infection related to surgery. (10 marks)

(b) Describe the management of Mrs. Oyibo after the operation under the following headings:

- i. relief of pain (4 marks)
- ii. drainage tube and skin care (6 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

Papa Hindocha, a 70 year old man is admitted to the surgical ward with a diagnosis of cancer of the larynx. He is booked for total laryngectomy.

(a) Describe how you would prepare him psychologically before surgery, especially regarding the outcome of the laryngectomy.

(7marks)

(b) State the gerontological assessment you would carry out on Papa Hindocha. (4 marks)

(c) Describe how you would care for the tracheostomy tube in situ. (9 marks)

12510 URM

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING, REGISTERED MIDWIFERY AND
REGISTERED MENTAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

AUGUST 2015

PAPER IIIB: PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Measles is a highly infectious childhood disease with high fatality rates.

- a. Describe **NINE (9)** common signs and symptoms of measles. (9 marks)
- b. Mention **SIX (6)** complications of a child with severe measles. (3 marks)
- c. Describe the **control** measures of measles. (8 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

A village community was identified to dispose off their dry refuse indiscriminately.

- a. How would you convince the community members to desist from this practice (8 marks)
- b. How would you advice the use of the following methods for disposing of their refuse?
 - I. Incineration (5 marks)
 - II. Composting (5 marks)
- c. State **FOUR (4)** advantages of incineration? (2 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. State **FOUR (4)** benefits of family planning **EACH** to the mother and child. (8 marks)
- b. Describe the instructions you will give to a client on the use of:
 - i. Male condom (6 marks)
 - ii. Female condom (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH - 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER II: MIDWIFERY

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Madam Akua Mainoo, 28 years old, gravida 3, para 1+1, has reported at the antenatal clinic for booking.

- (a) What past obstetric history would you take from her? *Alsch, CS, Post-term, still birth, force delivery* (6 marks)
PPV
- (b) Describe the education that would be given to Madam Akua on nutrition. (6 marks)
- (c) What advice would you give to Madam Akua in relation to the following minor disorders of pregnancy:
- i. heart burn (4 marks)
 - ii. constipation (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

The partograph is a tool used for monitoring progress of labour.

- (a) Explain SEVEN advantages of the partograph to a student midwife on your ward. (7 marks)
- (b) State THREE categories of pregnant women who do not qualify for the use of the partograph. (3 marks)

QUESTION THREE CONT'D

- (b) Give SIX causes of bleeding in early pregnancy. (3 marks)
- (c) What advice will you give Madam Gado before discharge? (5 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

Madam Esi Brimah, multip of 2, 28 years old, delivered at the hospital on the 2/5/2005.

- (a) What examination will you carry out on her during the first one week using the following headings:
 - i. Breast (1 mark)
 - ii. Uterus (4 marks)
 - iii. Lochia (4 marks)(12 marks)
- (b) Madam Esi was brought to the hospital on the 10th day after delivery with a history of post partum haemorrhage. Describe how the midwife will manage her before the arrival of the doctor. (8 marks)

- ii. How would you assess maternal condition in labour? (2m)
- iii. Mention TWO groups of drugs that may be used during labour and give ONE example of each. (2marks)

QUESTION THREE

Madam Awusi Gado, with 6 weeks amenorrhoea, reports at the gynaecological clinic with slight vaginal bleeding. She complained of severe abdominal pain. Her general condition started deteriorating and ruptured ectopic gestation was suspected.

- a. How would you manage Madam Gado before the arrival of the doctor using the following headings:
- FIVE observations (5marks)
 - THREE physiological preparations for surgery (3marks)
 - FOUR psychological preparations for surgery (4marks)

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

- (c) How would you teach a junior nurse on the technique of handwashing?
(6 marks)
- (d) Enumerate FOUR complications that she may develop apart from infection.
(2 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mrs. Janet Ainoo, 46 years old, married with one child is admitted to your ward with breast cancer. She is for radical mastectomy.

- (a) State SIX predisposing factors of breast cancer.
(3 marks)
 - (b) State EIGHT signs and symptoms of breast cancer.
(8 marks)
 - (c) What education would you give to Mrs. Ainoo and her family pre operatively in order to help them adjust to her new image.
(7 marks)
 - (d) State TWO specific complications of mastectomy.
(2 marks)
-

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LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH - 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER IIIA: MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Yaa Ginn, 16 years old, had spontaneous delivery in your facility. You observed Yaa sitting on the bed, looking moody and just gazing at her baby who was crying. She was later diagnosed as suffering from depression.

- (a) Mention FIVE factors during the ante natal period that may lead to depression in the puerperium. (5 marks)
- (b) State EIGHT other signs and symptoms that Yaa will present. (4 marks)
- (c) How would you manage Yaa and the baby for the first 48 hours while at your facility? (11 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Adjo Avornyo, 27 years, gravida 2 para 1, is 10 weeks pregnant. She reports for antenatal care and reveals to the midwife that her first child, 4 years old is a Mongol (Down's syndrome). She is anxious and needs advice.

- (a) Mention SIX factors during labour and infancy that may be responsible for mental retardation. (3 marks)
 - (b) How would mental retardation affect the child? (7 marks)
-/2

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

- (c) What advice would you give to Adjo in order to reduce the risk of having another mentally retarded child? (10 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mame Yaa, 40 years old, gravida 12, para 11, all alive (girls) is on admission with the diagnosis of 34 weeks pregnancy with anxiety neurosis. On interviewing her you learnt that the husband was threatening to divorce her if she delivers another girl.

- (a) Explain in NOT more than 30 words the term "anxiety". (3 marks)
- (b) State TEN psychological features of anxiety. (5 marks)
- (c) How would you manage Mame Yaa in order to reduce the anxiety? (12 marks)

~~Nurses IR~~
SRN 910

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NURSES AND MIDWIVES' COUNCIL FOR GHANA
FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 1998

NURSING PAPER II (SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING,
ORTHOPAEDICS, UROLOGY AND GYNAECOLOGY)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant matter.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

1

Mrs. Ata, a forty-year old lady was admitted to your ward with cancer of the left breast. She has been booked for a radical mastectomy.

- (a) List FOUR clinical features associated with cancer of the breast. (4 marks)
 ① lump
 ② Retracted or inverted nipple
- (b) List THREE specific investigations that will be requested to confirm the diagnosis. (3 marks)
 ① Biopsy
 ② mammography
 ③ Bone Scan
 ③ Enlargement of axillary lymph nodes
 ④ Bleeding or disch.
- (c) Describe the post-operative management of Mrs. Ata during the first 48 hours. (5 marks)
 5 A in size of breast
- (d) How would you prepare her towards discharge and rehabilitation. (8 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Salifu sustained 2° burns of the chest and abdomen. As part of the treatment the surgeon has decided to do skin grafting.

- (a) Explain TWO types of skin grafting. (2 marks)
- (b) Enumerate FOUR indications for skin grafting (2 marks)
- (c) Outline the specific preparation for Mr. Salifu to ensure successful grafting. (8 marks)
- (d) Describe the care of the wounds after the grating. (8 marks)

2

QUESTION THREE

Mr. Kwesi Karikari was involved in a road traffic accident and sustained a simple fracture of the pelvis and a compound fracture of the left lower limb. He has a pelvic traction and a plaster of Paris (P.O.P.) on the left lower limb as part of the treatment.

- (a) What observations would you make on the limb and the wound during the first 48 hours after the application of the P.O.P.?
(6 marks)
- (b) Describe the care of Mr. Karikari under the following headings:
 - i. nutrition (4 marks)
 - ii. elimination (4 marks)
 - iii. rehabilitation (3 marks)
- (c) Mention THREE complications of fractured pelvis.
(3 marks)

Mr ~~Adu~~ ^{Gasiba} ~~Adu~~ is admitted with Cancer of the right kidney. He is scheduled for right nephrectomy

(a) Give two clinical manifestations of cancer of the kidney

- 1) Haematuria & no pain.
- 2) low grade ~~pain~~ temp.
- 3) wt loss
- 4) Anaemia
- 5) Bone pain.

(b) State the pre-op prep of Mr ~~Adu~~ Gasiba, under

i. For possible investigation

- 1. urine amp
- 2. kidney, yellow, bladder x-ray
- 3. Renal biopsy
- 4. CT scan

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

FEBRUARY 2016

PAPER IIID: PAEDIATRIC NURSING

ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS TO CANDIDATES

1. Answer all **THREE** questions.
2. Each question must be answered in a **separate answer booklet**.
3. Do not write in either margin.
4. Each question carries **20 marks**.
5. Read the question carefully and provide **ONLY** relevant answers.
6. No marks shall be awarded for irrelevant information.
7. **Note** that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks.

TIME ALLOWED: 1 ½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Ama Korkor, three years old, is diagnosed as having worm infestation

- a. State **FOUR (4)** common types of worms that Ama could be infested with and the **route** by which each of them infests the body (6 marks)
- b. Enumerate the effect of Ascariasis on the victim (7 marks)
- c. What education would you give to Ama's mother on prevention of worm infestation (7 marks)

TOTAL = 20 Marks

QUESTION TWO

Maame Ama, 3 years old is on admission with measles. She is on an antibiotic mixture among other drugs.

- a. State only **FIVE (5)** general rules guiding the administration of medication to children (5 marks)
- b. Describe how you would administer co-trimozazole mixture to Maame Ama (9 marks)
- c. Describe the **SPECIFIC** procedure to administer a rectal paracetamol suppository to her to reduce her temperature (6 marks)

Total = 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Michael, 9 years old, has a simple fractured femur. He has just been brought from the casualty theatre after manipulation and application of P.O.P

- a. State **SIX (6)** signs and symptoms of fracture that Michael would present. (3 marks)
- b. State **FOUR (4)** expected patient outcomes that you would base your nursing care on while managing Michael. (4 marks)
- c. Describe the general management of Michael while at the casualty unit. (13 marks)

Total = 20 marks

See copy

**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING
EXAMINATION - MARCH 2006**

PAPER IIID (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A twelve day old baby Kodjo is admitted to the ward with the diagnosis of pyloric stenosis. He is booked for operation.

- (a) Explain the term pyloric stenosis. (4 marks)
- (b) Write FIVE assessment findings the nurse will make which indicate that Kodjo actually has pyloric stenosis. (5 marks)
- (c) List TWO types of operation that can be done for an infant with pyloric stenosis. (2 marks)
- (d) Describe how you would manage Kodjo pre-operatively. (9 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Esi, a pre-term baby, is admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) for expert care.

- (a) What do you understand by the word "pre-term?" (2 marks)
- (b) Outline THREE measures by which the rate of pre-term births can be reduced. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

(c) State THREE abnormalities EACH, that you would observe, record and report on the underlisted when nursing the pre-term baby.

- i. colour
- ii. respiration
- iii. feeding
- iv. skin
- v. stools

(15 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Aba Kakraba, 5 years old, is diagnosed as having worm infestation.

(a) State FOUR common types of worms that Aba could be infested with, and describe the route by which each of them enters the body.

(6 marks)

(b) Mention the effects of ascariasis on the victim.

(7 marks)

(c) What education would you give to Aba's mother on prevention of worm infestation in Aba?

(7 marks)

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

JANUARY 2009

PAPER II: SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all FOUR questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A thirty-five-year-old lady, Yaa Asantewaa, was rushed to the emergency unit of your hospital with generalized abdominal pains. She was diagnosed as having ruptured ectopic pregnancy.

- (a) Explain ruptured ectopic pregnancy to a first year student. (4 marks)
- (b) Enumerate SIX predisposing conditions to ectopic pregnancy. (6 marks)
- (c) State EIGHT clinical features that would be exhibited by Madam Yaa Asantewaa. (4 marks)
- (d) Describe the nursing intervention for Madam Yaa Asantewaa under the headings:
 - i. Pain (3 marks)
 - ii. Grieving (3 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Beak with large goitre is scheduled for a subtotal thyroidectomy to treat thyrotoxicosis.

- (a) State TEN clinical features of toxic goitre. (5 marks)
- (b) List FOUR specific diagnostic investigations of toxic goitre. (5 marks)
- (c) Describe the post-operative nursing management of Mrs. Beak for the first 48 hours. (8 marks)
- (d) List FOUR side effects of antithyroid drugs. (2 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Describe how you would prepare a patient for the following investigations after the procedure has been explained:

- (a) Barium meal (5 marks)
- (b) Bronchoscopy (4 marks)
- (c) Thoracentesis (6 marks)
- (d) Lumbar puncture (5 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

QUESTION FOUR

Ms. Aba Krampah, aged 25 is admitted to your ward with a discharging sinus on her left upper arm for 6 months. On examination and investigations, she was diagnosed as osteomyelitis secondary to sickle cell disease.

- (a) List FOUR major organisms causing osteomyelitis. (4 marks)
- (b) Describe how you would take a wound swab from Aba's discharging arm. (Trolley has been sent to the bedside). (10 marks)
- (c) Name TWO possible surgical treatments for osteomyelitis. (2 marks)
- (d) What education would you give to patient on discharge? (4 marks)

TOTAL - 20 MARKS

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**REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING
EXAMINATION - MARCH 2006**

PAPER IIIA (MENTAL HEALTH/PsYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Adamu, a patient on your ward, was seen by the medical officer who diagnosed him as suffering from a psychosomatic disorder, precisely peptic ulcer.

- (a) Explain the term psychosomatic disorder (NOT MORE THAN 35 WORDS)
(3 marks)
- (b) What support would you give to Mr. Adamu under the following headings:
 - i. psychological (10 marks)
 - ii. physical (7 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mr. Eku, 32 years old alcoholic, is admitted to the surgical ward with burns of the left leg for skin grafting. A day prior to the operation he started showing signs of confusion and restlessness. The doctor made a provisional diagnosis of alcoholic hallucinosis and put him under observation.

- (a) Outline the history that you would obtain to help establish the fact that the patient is dependent on alcohol.
(6 marks)
- (b) List SIX factors that contribute to alcoholism.
(6 marks)
- (c) Describe how you would manage the patient for the first 48 hours after the provisional diagnosis has been made.
(8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

I. Kiki, an 18 year old boy, was admitted to your ward in a state of status epilepticus.

(a) Explain the condition "status epilepticus". (3 marks)

(b) Give THREE possible precipitating factors that can lead to status epilepticus in a patient with epilepsy.

(3 marks)

(c) Describe how you would manage Kiki on the ward. (10 marks)

II. A schizophrenic patient in your ward is granted 7 days parole by his doctor.

Give FOUR benefits that the patient will derive from going home for this short period.

(4 marks)

(b)

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REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION - MARCH 2006

PAPER I (MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers. No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

✓ RM

Ama Serwah, an 18 year old student was treated with tablets for malaria. She was rushed back to the hospital unconscious. During physical assessment, she started to fit, and was diagnosed as having cerebral malaria.

- (a) Explain the term "cerebral malaria." (3 marks)
- (b) What will be your immediate nursing responsibilities for Ama? (6 marks)
- (c) Describe how you will assess Ama Serwah's level of consciousness. (10 marks)
- (d) Give ONE differential diagnosis of cerebral malaria. (1 mark)

QUESTION TWO

Theresa, a 36 year old waitress and a single parent, lives in a single room with her two daughters. She has been diagnosed as having bacterial pneumonia.

- (a) List SIX clinical manifestations that Theresa will present. (3 marks)
- (b) Using the NURSING PROCESS as a framework, formulate the objective/outcome criteria and nursing intervention for the following nursing diagnoses:
 - i. ineffective airway clearance related to inability to cough effectively. (6 marks)
 - ii. activity intolerance related to dyspnoea (5 marks)
 - iii. knowledge deficit related to home care (6 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Wendy, a nurse working at the haemodialysis unit, presented with jaundice, abdominal pain, nausea and vomiting, easy fatiguability and pale coloured stools. Based on laboratory investigations, a diagnosis of hepatitis B was established.

- (a) State the mode of transmission of hepatitis B infection. (2 marks)
- (b) Describe how you would manage Wendy under the following headings:
- i. nutrition (4 marks)
 - ii. rest (2 marks)
 - iii. prevention of spread of infection (8 marks)
- (c) State FOUR risk factors that may contribute to the transmission of hepatitis B. (4 marks)

QUESTION FOUR

Mr. Osei Wusu, a 65 year old farmer, is admitted to your ward with rheumatoid arthritis.

- (a) List TEN clinical manifestations he will present. (5 marks)
- (b) Describe the pathophysiology of rheumatoid arthritis. (4 marks)
- (c) What will be your nursing intervention under:
- i. pain relief (5 marks)
 - ii. education (to the patient and family) (6 marks)
-

**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED COMMUNITY HEALTH AND REGISTERED
MIDWIFERY LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIA: PSYCHIATRIC/MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions

Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet

Each question carries 20 marks

Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.

No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mrs. Yawa Bronya, a 30-year-old alcoholic is admitted to the female admission ward with severe anaemia.

- (a) State FIVE nursing diagnoses that relate to Mr. Bronya's alcoholic state.
(5 marks)
- (b) Describe any TEN steps you would take in the psychological management of the patient in the first 48 hours of admission.
(10 marks)
- (c) Describe FIVE ways in which you will give emotional support to the patient's family.
(5 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Ms. Adwoa Mensah was referred to the community psychiatric nurse after 6 weeks of admission to the psychiatric hospital for continuity of care.

- (a) Outline FOUR ways in which the community psychiatric nurse will be useful to Ms. Adwoa and her family.

(4 marks)

- (b) While in the ward, how would the nurse know if Ms. Adwoa Mensah was ready to be discharged?

(5 marks)

- (c) How would the nurse organize and ensure adequate participation in diversional activities in the ward?

(8 marks)

- (d) State SIX benefits that a patient can derive from occupational therapy. (OT)

(3 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Ms. Nelly has been admitted to Ward 6 of the General Hospital with complaints of dryness of mouth, increased heart beat and sleepless nights. She was diagnosed as suffering from anxiety reaction.

- (a) Discuss FOUR ways by which Ms. Nelly's behaviour will disturb her family members.

(4 marks)

- (b) Outline TEN reasons why a patient will refuse food.

(5 marks)

- (c) Enumerate EIGHT reasons why Ms. Nelly will have sleepless nights in the ward.

(4 marks)

- (d) What nursing management will you render to Ms. Nelly?

(7 marks)

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER I (MEDICINE AND MEDICAL NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL FOUR QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mrs. Ansah is on admission with acute renal failure on account of intake of herbal preparation for chronic constipation which led to severe diarrhoea. She is on peritoneal dialysis.

- (a) How would you explain acute renal failure to a student nurse? (7 marks)
- (b) List FOUR main causes of acute renal failure. (4 marks)
- (c) What would you tell a student nurse who wants to know why Mrs. Ansah is on peritoneal dialysis? (6 marks)
- (d) State THREE complications of peritoneal dialysis. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Madam Bediako, a 32 year old trader is rushed to the casualty department with severe shortness of breath, cough, wheezing and fatigue. She is diagnosed as suffering from acute bronchial asthma.

- (a) Mention FOUR factors that may precipitate an attack of Bronchial Asthma. (2 marks)
- (b) Draw a comprehensive plan for the care of Madam Bediako under the following headings using the clinical manifestations below:
 - i. shortness of breath
 - ii. cough
 - iii. fatigue

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

- Nursing diagnosis (3 marks)
- Objective/outcome criteria (3 marks)
- Nursing intervention (9 marks)

(c) Enumerate SIX complications of asthma. (3 marks)

QUESTION THREE ✓ RGH

Madam Esi Pokua is admitted with cerebrovascular accident (CVA) on your ward.

- (a) Describe TWO ways in which blood supply to the brain is interrupted in CVA. (4 marks)
- (b) List EIGHT neurological signs and symptoms that Madam Pokua would present. (4 marks)
- (c) Describe the management of Madam Pokua under the following headings:

- i. nutrition (5 marks)
- ii. drug therapy (2 marks)
- iii. physical rehabilitation (5 marks)

QUESTION FOUR ✓ RM

- (a) As a staff nurse, describe how you would prepare and conduct ward rounds. (8 marks)
 - (b) How would you "barrier nurse" a patient suffering from typhoid fever in the main ward? (8 marks)
 - (c) Describe how you would manage a patient who develops anaphylactic shock after being given injection penicillin? (4 marks)
-

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**REGISTERED GENERAL, REGISTERED MENTAL HEALTH AND REGISTERED
COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION**

JANUARY 2009

PAPER IIIC: OBSTETRIC NURSING

ESSAY

Answer all three questions
Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
Each question carries 20 marks
Read the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

(a) With the aid of a well labelled diagram covering about one third of a page, describe the microscopic structure of the breast.

(12 marks)

(b) State the benefits of breastfeeding under the following headings:

i. Mother (three benefits) (3 marks)

ii. Baby (five benefits) (5 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION TWO

Madam Akoto was rushed to the labour ward shortly after spontaneous delivery of a baby girl on her way to the hospital.

- (a) Describe how you will manage the third stage of labour. (12 marks)
- (b) Describe SIX observations that would be recorded on completion of the 3rd stage of labour. (6 marks)
- (c) Mention FOUR drugs used in controlling haemorrhage during the 3rd stage of labour. (2 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

QUESTION THREE

Examination of the newborn is paramount in obstetric nursing because it affords the opportunity to detect early and manage any abnormalities that might pose danger to the newborn.

- (a) Describe the examination you would conduct on a newly born baby under the following headings:
- i. Head and face (8 marks)
 - ii. Trunk (5 marks)
 - iii. Upper and lower extremities (5 marks)
 - iv. Genitalia (2 marks)

TOTAL – 20 MARKS

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LICENSURE EXAMINATION FOR DIRECT MIDWIFERY
4TH – 9TH MAY 2005

PAPER IIIA: MENTAL HEALTH NURSING

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Yaa Ginn, 16 years old, had spontaneous delivery in your facility. You observed Yaa sitting on the bed, looking moody and just gazing at her baby who was crying. She was later diagnosed as suffering from depression.

- (a) Mention FIVE factors during the ante natal period that may lead to depression in the puerperium. (5 marks)
- (b) State EIGHT other signs and symptoms that Yaa will present. (4 marks)
- (c) How would you manage Yaa and the baby for the first 48 hours while at your facility? (11 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Adjo Avornyo, 27 years, gravida 2 para 1, is 10 weeks pregnant. She reports for antenatal care and reveals to the midwife that her first child, 4 years old is a Mongol (Down's syndrome). She is anxious and needs advice.

- (a) Mention SIX factors during labour and infancy that may be responsible for mental retardation. (3 marks)
 - (b) How would mental retardation affect the child? (7 marks)
-/2

QUESTION TWO CONT'D

- (c) What advice would you give to Adjo in order to reduce the risk of having another mentally retarded child? (10 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mame Yaa, 40 years old, gravida 12, para 11, all alive (girls) is on admission with the diagnosis of 34 weeks pregnancy with anxiety neurosis. On interviewing her you learnt that the husband was threatening to divorce her if she delivers another girl.

- (a) Explain in NOT more than 30 words the term "anxiety". (3 marks)
- (b) State TEN psychological features of anxiety. (5 marks)
- (c) How would you manage Mame Yaa in order to reduce the anxiety? (12 marks)
-

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NURSES AND MIDWIVES' COUNCIL FOR GHANA
NATIONAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 1991
NURSING PAPER III 'A' (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

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27

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant matter. Credit will be given for simple, clear, legible handwriting, good English and orderly organization of material.

BOTH QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

TIME ALLOWED: 1 HOUR

QUESTION ONE

Miss Ranayatu Ibrahim, aged 21 years, was admitted to your ward with diagnosis of Acute (Toxic) confusional state.

- (a) What is Acute (Toxic) confusional state? (2 marks)
- (b) List six (6) causes of Acute (Toxic) state (6 marks)
- (c) Enumerate five (5) physical and five (5) psychological features that Miss Ibrahim would exhibit. (10 marks)
- (d) Describe the management that would be given to the patient until her discharge. (20 marks)

Presentation - 2 marks
 Total - 40 marks

QUESTION TWO

Write notes on the following:

- (a) Recreational Therapy (14 marks)
- (b) Epanutin (Phenytoin Sodium) (10 marks)
- (c) Homosexuality (10 marks)
- (d) Stupor (6 marks)

Total - 40 marks

Stupor
mute
- depressed
- conscious & intact
ES happens

Rest
disc
Psychotherapy
side
Ch
personal hygiene
S. Medication

PRELIMINARY STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 1999

FIRST AID AND BANDAGING

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Johnny White was involved in a road traffic accident and sustained injury to the right thigh which appeared to be a compound fracture of the right femur.

- (a) Give SIX signs and symptoms that Mr. White will manifest. (6 marks)
- (b) Describe the first aid treatment that would be given to Mr. White. (10 marks)
- (c) What information would be given to the doctor on arrival to the hospital. (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO

A quarrel between Mr and Mrs. Adobo led to fierce fighting in which Mr. Adobo stabbed Mrs. Adobo with the ragged end of a broken bottle in the abdomen.

- (a) Describe the type of wound that Mrs. Adobo would sustain. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe the first aid management that would be given to Mrs. Adobo. (15 marks)
- (c) List TWO immediate complications that may arise from the injury. (2 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Describe the first aid management of the following:

- (a) Grit in the eye. (5 marks)
- (b) Fainting attack (6 marks)
- (c) Bleeding from the nose (4 marks)
- (d) Snake bite of the foot (5 marks)

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PRELIMINARY STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 1999

PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) Draw a well labelled diagram of the skin. (5 marks)
- (b) Describe the structure of the epidermis (5 marks)
- (c) Describe FIVE functions of the skin (10 marks)

QUESTION TWO

- (a) Describe the ankle joint. (7 marks)
- (b) Illustrate your answer with a well labelled diagram. (4 marks)
- (c) Name TWO muscles that take part in producing movement at the joint. (2 marks)
- (d) Name the bones that form the foot. (4 marks)
- (e) List THREE functions of the arches of the foot. (3 marks)

QUESTION THREE

List FOUR functions of each of the following:

- (a) Peritoneum
- (b) Bone marrow
- (c) Tissue fluid (4 marks each)
- (d) Spleen
- (e) Vertebral column

3 P M O E D C

- Admit reassure
Do looction
MNS Ngahim
feeding
hydra
obs
preservation
drugs

sponging
mouth care
side effect

Vitals
weight
urine out put
fluid intake
o demu
sleeping & eating
behaviour
working
colour
firmness
LO
3 30
4

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NMTC, BEREKUM

FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - AUGUST, 2000
NURSING PAPER III 'D' (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

An 8-year old girl is brought to the paediatric ward unconscious and has been provisionally diagnosed as having cerebral malaria.

high temp
severe head

- (a) List SIX clinical features that this patient will present. (6 marks)
- (b) Describe how you would care for her for the first 24 hours on admission. (15 marks)
- X(c) What investigations may be done to confirm the diagnosis? (1 mark)
- (d) Enumerate THREE complications that may occur. (3 marks)

QUESTION TWO

A 10-year old boy Kodjo Atta is admitted to the children's ward with the diagnosis of nephrotic syndrome.

- (a) Explain the term nephrotic syndrome. (3 marks)
- (b) What observations will you make on Kodjo Atta during the first week of admission? (12 marks)
- (c) What advice will you give the parents on the care of Kodjo Atta at home? (10 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- I. (a) State FIVE indications for performing tracheostomy in children. (5 marks)
- (b) How would you reduce anxiety for the child and his parents in relation to tracheostomy? (5 marks)
- II. Baby Esi Quansah, 9 months old is admitted to your ward with intussusception.

FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 2000
NURSING PAPER III 'A' (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. Duah, 40, a casual labourer, is admitted to the medical ward with acute urinary tract infection. Two days later he started presenting features of catatonic excitation.

- (a) List EIGHT factors that may precipitate the onset of schizophrenia. (8 marks)
- (b) List TEN features of the excitement phase of catatonia. (5 marks)
- (c) Outline the nursing management of Mr. Duah for the first 48 hours of diagnosis of catatonia. (12 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Madam Akua Esson, 38, is admitted to the surgical ward with oophoritis. She is scheduled for oophorectomy. She has started exhibiting symptoms of anxiety.

- (a) State SIX physical and SIX psychological signs and symptoms of anxiety. (6 marks)
- (b) Describe how you will manage Madam Esson physically and psychologically. (15 marks)
- (c) List FOUR ways by which a person can manifest features of conversion hysteria. (4 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) List SIX causes of acute organic reaction under the following headings.
 - (i) infection (3 marks)
 - (ii) metabolic and endocrine disorders (3 marks)
- (b) i. Define senile dementia and mental retardation. (6 marks)
ii. Tabulate THREE differences between the two conditions defined (6 marks)
- (c) Explain the following ego defence mechanisms. Give example to illustrate your answer.
 - (i) displacement (3 marks)
 - (ii) reaction formation (4 marks)

NURSES AND MIDWIVES' COUNCIL FOR GHANA
FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 1997
NURSING PAPER III 'A' (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

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NMTG, BEREKUM

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE.

Mr. John Ocloo, 52, was admitted to the medical ward for a medical check up. In the second week he started manifesting psychiatric features and the psychiatrist was informed.

State the psychological observations that you would make on the patient in the first 48 hours regarding

- (a) eating (3 marks)
- (b) sleeping (4 marks)
- (c) motor activities (6 marks)
- (d) speech (8 marks)
- (e) mood (4 marks)

QUESTION TWO.

Ms. Ramatu Musah, an 18 year old girl is admitted to the medical ward with malaria. Five days later, she started presenting features of mania.

- (a) List FOUR factors that may precipitate the onset of mania. (5 marks)
- (b) List EIGHT signs and symptoms that Ms. Musah would present (8 marks)
- (c) Describe the nursing management of Ms. Musah (12 marks)

QUESTION THREE.

- (a) Mr. Kofi Drobo, a 47 year old farm labourer was admitted to your ward with a provisional diagnosis of delirium tremens.
 - i) In not more than THIRTY words explain what is meant by delirium tremens (2 marks)
 - ii) List SIX physical and SIX psychological signs and symptoms of delirium tremens (12 marks)
 - iii) Describe the medical treatment that may be prescribed. for Mr. Drobo. (3 marks)
- (b) Describe the clinical manifestations of petit mal seizure. (8 marks)

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NURSES AND MIDWIVES' COUNCIL FOR GHANA
FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - AUGUST, 1989

NURSING PAPER III 'A' (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant matter. Credit will be given for simple, clear, legible handwriting, good English and orderly organization of material.

BOTH QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

TIME ALLOWED: 1 HOUR

QUESTION ONE

Observation and accurate reporting are important functions of the psychiatric nurse.

Outline five (5) points of observation that will be made by the nurse on a newly admitted mentally-ill patient.

(40 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Refusal of food is one of the causes for admission of patients to the psychiatric hospital.

(a) Give eight (8) reasons why patients refuse to eat.

(16 marks)

(b) Describe the management of the patient.

(24 marks)

Total - 40 marks

*(Kamie
Schizo
depressive
drug addicts -*

Sub copy

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION - MARCH 2006

PAPER IIIB (PUBLIC HEALTH NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers. No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1 1/2 HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) List SIX common water borne diseases. (3 marks)
(b) Explain how water can be contaminated in the home. (5 marks)
(c) Outline the points you would highlight in a talk to a rural community on making water safe for drinking. (12 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Statistics from the district health directorate indicate an increase in the number of reported cases of tuberculosis.

- (a) What are the factors that facilitate the spread of tuberculosis? (7 marks)
(b) Outline FIVE important areas you will stress on when educating a young mother with a diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis who is nursing a two month old baby. (5 marks)
(c) What points will you highlight in your education to a group in your community regarding the prevention of pulmonary tuberculosis? (8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

A teenager seeks advice on how to care for her 72 year old grand father.

Describe how you would educate her on the following:

- a. nutrition (5 marks)
b. prevention of home accidents (5 marks)
c. physical care (5 marks)
d. psychological care (5 marks)

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FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 2000
NURSING PAPER III'D' (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 25 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Master Francis Dzinu, aged 5 years, has been admitted with severe anaemia caused by sickle cell disease.

- (a) List SIX other causes of haemolytic anaemia. (6 marks)
- (b) Enumerate TEN clinical features of sickle cell anaemia. (5 marks)
- (c) Describe the health education you would give to Master Dzinu's mother on discharge regarding the prevention of sickle cell crisis. (14 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Master Kwame Doe, aged 6 years, has been brought to the accident and emergency ward with a simple fracture of the right femur. He is for application of P.O.P.

- (a) State SIX clinical features that would make you conclude that he has a simple fracture of the femur. (6 marks)
- (b) Describe how you would care for Kwame and the P.O.P. for the first 24 hours. (14 marks)
- (c) Enumerate FIVE features that would make you call the doctor urgently after the application of the P.O.P. (5 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Master Kojo Donkor, aged five years, has been admitted to your ward with provisional diagnosis of bacterial meningitis.

- (a) List FIVE signs and symptoms that he may present (5 marks)
- (b) What FOUR specific investigations will confirm the diagnosis? (4 marks)
- (c) Enumerate THREE types of drugs that may be prescribed for him. (6 marks)
- (d) Outline the nursing care that would be given to Master

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REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER III D (PAEDIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Yaw Biritwum, 6 years old, is admitted into the paediatric ward with a temperature of 39°C, anorexia and dysuria. He has been diagnosed as having urinary tract infection.

- (a) Give the pathophysiology of urinary tract infection. (8 marks)
- (b) Outline THREE objectives in the nursing management of Yaw Biritwum. (6 marks)
- (c) Describe THREE nursing interventions that you will perform for Yaw to help you achieve your aim. (6 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Sule Moro, 3 years old, is admitted to your ward with Hirschsprung's disease for surgery.

- (a) Give EIGHT clinical manifestations of Hirschsprung's disease. (4 marks)
- (b) State FIVE nursing objectives in relation to Sule Moro's pre-operative care. (5 marks)
- (c) Describe the specific post-operative nursing management of Sule Moro. (11 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Isaac Doe, 4 years old, is admitted with severe anaemia caused by sickle-cell disease.

- (a) List FOUR other causes of haemolytic anaemia. (4 marks)
- (b) Enumerate EIGHT clinical features of sickle-cell disease. (4 marks)
- (c) What health education would you give to Isaac's mother on discharge regarding the prevention of sickle-cell crisis? (12 marks)

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10th and 9th

NURSES AND MIDWIVES' COUNCIL FOR GHANA
FINAL STATE REGISTERED MENTAL NURSES EXAMINATION
FEBRUARY, 1990

PAPER I - PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICE OF PSYCHIATRIC NURSING
ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant matter. Credit will be given for simple, clear, legible handwriting, good English and orderly organization of material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

It is said that Schizophrenia forms about 1% of the world population and about 70% of the in-patients in the State Psychiatric Hospitals are Schizophrenics.

1. Schizophrenia
2. 70%
3. 1%

- (a) What is Schizophrenia? (4 marks)
- (b) List six (6) cardinal signs and symptoms of Schizophrenia. (6 marks)
- (c) Outline the nursing care and management of a patient suffering from Schizophrenia. (9 marks)

ORDEP
Obscure
Delusional
Disorganized
Disturbed
Disorientation

Presentation - 1 mark
Total - 20 marks

QUESTION TWO

1. per group
2. Emotional
3. No lab
4. Age
5. 10%

Substance Abuse is said to be a global problem, which tends to be on the increase.

- (a) What is Substance Abuse? (2 marks)
- (b) Enumerate five (5) aetiologic factors of substance abuse which may be found in the personality structure of the individual. (5 marks)
- (c) List ten (10) substances which may be included on a list of substance abuse. (5 marks)
- (d) Outline how a patient with the problems of substance abuse would be managed. (8 marks)

1. Alcohol
2. Heroin
3. Cocaine
4. Amphetamines
5. Prochlorperazine
6. Valium
7. Ephedrine
8. Tobacco
9. Coffee
10. Alcohol

Total - 20 marks

QUESTION THREE

Write notes on:

- (a) La belle indifference (5 marks)
- (b) Juvenile Courts (5 marks)
- ✓(c) Psychodynamics (5 marks)
- ✓(d) Free Association (5 marks)

Total - 20 marks

REGISTERED GENERAL NURSING DIPLOMA LICENSURE
EXAMINATION - 25TH-28TH MARCH, 2002

PAPER III 'A' (PSYCHIATRIC NURSING)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

A known epileptic patient (grand mal) is having an attack of status epilepticus and is admitted to the medical ward.

- (a) Describe how you would nurse the patient until he fully recovers. (10 marks)
- (b) Describe TEN areas you would stress when giving education to this patient after recovery. (10 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Madam Ama Eni, 38, was taken ill suddenly and was brought to the emergency ward of your hospital. She was later diagnosed as suffering from hypomania.

- (a) List TEN signs and symptoms that Madam Eni would present. (5 marks)
- (b) Describe the nursing management of Madam Eni for the first 48 hours in your ward. (15 marks)

QUESTION THREE

Mr. Baako was admitted at the psychiatric ward this morning on account of delirium tremens.

- (a) Explain the term delirium tremens. (3 marks)
- (b) List FIVE psychological and FIVE physical signs and symptoms that Mr. Baako would present. (5 marks)
- (c) Describe the nursing management of Mr. Baako. (12 marks)

COMMUNITY HEALTH NURSING LICENSING EXAMINATION

DECEMBER 2006

PAPER IA: (PERSONAL AND COMMUNITY HYGIENE, COMMUNICABLE DISEASES AND SCHOOL HEALTH

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and provide only relevant answers.
No marks will be given for irrelevant information.

**ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED
EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS**

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

- (a) Enumerate FIVE common causes of anaemia in school children. (5 marks)
- (b) State the signs and symptoms of worm infestation. (5 marks)
- (c) Describe TEN preventive measures which will help reduce worm infestation. (10 marks)

QUESTION TWO

During a community study at Kyekye-were, you observed that the community has poor drainage system.

- (a) Explain SIX hazards associated with poor drainage to the community members. (12 marks)
- (b) Describe FOUR measures you would take to ensure good drainage of waste water in the community. (8 marks)

QUESTION THREE

A mother brings her 8 month-old infant with fever and diarrhoea to your clinic. The infant has had his immunization up to date. As a community officer (CHO);

- (a) What assessment will you make? (6 marks)
 - (b) How would you manage this child? (9 marks)
 - (c) What education would you give to the mother before she takes the child home? (5 marks)
-

Self copy

FINAL STATE EXAMINATION - FEBRUARY, 2001
S.R.N. PAPER II (SURGERY AND SURGICAL NURSING
ORTHOPAEDICS, UROLOGY AND GYNAECOLOGY)

ESSAY

IMPORTANT: READ the questions carefully and answer only what is asked. No marks will be given for irrelevant material.

ALL THREE QUESTIONS MUST BE ANSWERED

EACH QUESTION CARRIES 20 MARKS

TIME ALLOWED: 1½ HOURS

QUESTION ONE

Mr. John Yabu, 48 years, is admitted to the hospital with haemorrhoids. He had haemorrhoidectomy done and has been brought to the ward unconscious.

- (a) State FOUR signs and symptoms of haemorrhoids. (2 marks)
- (b) How would you care for the patient for the first 72 hours after the operation. (11 marks)
- (c) What measures would you take to prevent wound infection in the ward? (7 marks)

QUESTION TWO

Mrs. Efuah Kona, 32 years, is admitted in a collapsed state diagnosed as a ruptured ectopic pregnancy.

- (a) In not more than FIFTY words explain the term, ruptured ectopic pregnancy. (4 marks)
- (b) State EIGHT clinical features that Mrs. Kona will present. (4 marks)
- (c) What would be your pre-operative preparation before sending the patient to the theatre? (12 marks)

QUESTION THREE

- (a) Describe the post-operative management for the first 48 hours of a 30-year-old man who has had Caldwell-Luc operation and is brought to the ward fully conscious. (10 marks)

- (b) Describe the steps you will go through in scrubbing-up to assist in surgical operation. (Exclude gloving). (10 marks)